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Communication Enhancement Strategies to Mitigate Functional Siloes in Head Start Programs

Maryom G. McCloud
Walden University

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Walden University

College of Management and Human Potential

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Maryom G. McCloud

has been found to be complete and satisfactory in all respects,
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the review committee have been made.

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Walden University
2025

Abstract

Communication Enhancement Strategies to Mitigate Functional Siloes in Head Start
Programs

by

Maryom G. McCloud

MBA, DeVry University Keller Graduate School of Management, 2011

BMA, Charleston Southern University, 2005

Doctoral Study Submitted in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree of
Doctor of Business Administration

Walden University

June 2025

Abstract

Inefficient internal communication between program and financial operations may negatively affect organizational performance and profitability. Some Head Start Program (HSP) leaders are concerned with communication failures because of the potential to negatively impact business productivity and profitability. Grounded in business process re-engineering, the purpose of this qualitative single case study was to explore strategies used by HSP leaders to increase communications between program and financial operations to increase profitability. The participants were four HSP leaders located in the Northern Region of the United States, who successfully implemented such strategies. Data were collected from semistructured interviews and company documents. Through thematic analysis, five themes emerged: (a) leadership role, (b) organizational culture change, (c) meeting frequency and inclusive attendance, (d) access to data, and (e) training. A key recommendation is for HSP leaders to invest in financial training for program managers by providing resources. The implications for positive social change include the potential for HSP leaders to enhance employee workplace experiences through improved communication strategies, thereby strengthening service quality for underserved communities.

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Dedication

This case study is dedicated to the memory of my one and only son Daiquan Ernest Levelle Fox whom I lost at the tender age of 17. I am grateful to God that we were able to successfully navigate and mitigate the communication silos of parenting in those rough teen years before you departed. Not one day goes by that I do not apply those “parent hell” lessons to other mentees, staff, supervisors, and/or parents that reach out to me for wise counsel. You gave me the credentials and experience to provide relevant and rich context to the fabric of every encounter. I love you forever.

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Section 1: Foundation of the Study

Some Head Start Program leaders lack strategies to improve organizational performance and increase communications between program and financial operations. Communication barriers negatively impact business productivity and profitability (Zadorozhnyi et al., 2021). In 2017, researchers identified neglected internal communication practices at 1601 European corporations, nonprofit, and governmental organizations (Zerfass et al., 2017). The communication strategies that were explored through the study may help leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations. Leaders may be able to utilize the successful strategies of the Northern Region of the United States Head Start program leaders to improve their organizational performance.

Background of the Problem

The study of leadership strategies to increase internal communication can provide leaders with proven strategies to mitigate communication failures in their organizations. Functional silos within organizations create barriers that prohibit effective internal communication (Garcia, 2022). Organizations with a legacy of silos did not have a need for effective internal communications or consultation between departments as long as the job was successfully completed (Garcia, 2022). Garcia (2022) touted that the silo approach to service delivery and administrative operations must be realigned to enhance sustainability in organizations. Inefficient internal communications negatively impact overall organizational productivity, culture, profitability, innovation, and efficiency. According to Prescott (2023), functional silo syndrome interferes with creativity, talent

development, and the recognition of shared goals. Functional silo syndrome occurs in organizations when individual departments or functions are strong and efficient but the communication or connection between them is weak (Kwahk & Kim, 2004). According to Kwahk and Kim (2004), reducing the problem of functional silo syndrome enhanced operational and cost effectiveness. The goal of the study was to help leaders understand strategies used by other leaders to increase internal communications within their organizations successfully. Neill and Jiang (2017) indicated that a primary reason to address internal communications strategically was to align corporate culture, motivate employees by facilitating engagement and commitment, communicate organizational change, increase profitability, improve productivity, and support the exchange of data or information critical to the decision-making process. Sustaining change requires a shift in organizational dynamics and culture (Stauffer & Maxwell, 2020). It was important to identify both effective and ineffective internal communication channels. Ineffective internal communications should be identified so that training can be conducted to correct deficiencies (Raley et al., 2017). Effective internal communication channels should be identified and mirrored throughout the organization. Murphy and Campbell (2017) examined strategies that assessed the effectiveness of internal communications channels used by leaders and posited three themes for the development of communication strategies, which included informal assessment strategies, indirect assessment strategies, and efficient versus timely assessments. Strategies explored in the study may help leaders identify, assess, and correct internal communication issues; thereby, improving the overall agency.

Problem and Purpose

The specific business problem was that some Head Start Program leaders lack strategies to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Increasing the effectiveness of communication increases profitability (Neill & Jiang, 2017). Communication barriers negatively impact business productivity and profitability (Zadorozhnyi et al., 2021). The purpose of this qualitative single case study was to explore strategies used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. The target population consisted of four leaders from a Head Start Program in the Northern Region of the United States with multiple service locations who had demonstrated success in implementing strategies that increased communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability.

Population and Sampling

Data were collected from four leaders from a Head Start program located in the Northern Region of the United States with multiple service locations. Head Start Program leaders were interviewed using semistructured interviews designed to record their use of successful strategies for increasing communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Publicly available organizational documents were reviewed for relevant communication policies and information impacting the successful implementation of communication strategies. The sampling methods utilized in this case study were purposive and convenience. When research participants are deliberately selected to reflect specific characteristics such as age, location, industry, or species,

researchers define this as purposive sampling (Bullard, 2023). Researchers defined convenience sampling as a method in which participants are selected based on convenience, accessibility, and the willingness to participate (Wienclaw, 2023). These sampling methods were selected because participants will be recruited based on both their experience and accessibility.

Researchers suggest that participant eligibility criteria be based on robust research findings and consensus (Riel et al., 2022). To be eligible for participation in the study, the participant (a) must have been a past or present full-time employee for at least 2 years in a mid-level manager or senior executive role and (b) must have participated in the implementation of communication strategies to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. I had access to participants through prior work history. Recruitment to gain access to participants was a vital component to the success of this case study. I gained access to participants by recruiting them through direct email invitation. Researchers suggested a diversified recruitment strategy which incorporates the use of traditional recruitment methods, such as direct email invites and advertising, along with nontraditional methods such as social media (McNelis et al., 2023). The data sources used for the study were organizational documents and participant interview data. The combination of semistructured interviews and document analysis was used to collect appropriate data in support of addressing the conceptual framework and research questions in this study. Garrels et al. (2022) noted that the practicality and significance of in-depth interviews as a method for collecting rich narrative data adds value to qualitative research because participants often share

comprehensive information related to their lived experiences. Jameson (2017) supported this idea by stating that conducting semistructured interviews is the best interview method to use in qualitative research because the type of data collected from this interview method cannot be obtained using structured questionnaires, participant observation, or an analysis of the literature.

Nature of the Study

I chose the qualitative methodology for the study. Using the qualitative methodology enables researchers to explore and identify the participants' experiences and perspectives with the phenomena (Saunders et al., 2024). According to Saunders et al. (2024), the qualitative method is appropriate when the research intent is to explore business strategies and processes or human interaction. Thus, the qualitative method was appropriate for the study because the purpose of the study was to explore strategies used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communications between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Using the quantitative methodology enables researchers to examine and identify relationships among variables and to determine the generalizability of conclusions (Saunders et al., 2024). According to Nikmanesh and Mohd Nor (2019), the quantitative research method is focused on measuring causality and correlation between variables rather than the more critical analysis of the processes, which are often more important than the relationships between the variables, which was not the purpose of this study. Because a mixed-method study requires combining the quantitative and qualitative methods, I did not use the mixed-method approach because I

did not need the quantitative part. I concluded the qualitative research methodology was appropriate for the study's purpose.

The case study design was selected for this study. In the case study research design, data collected from participants are explored by researchers to gain an understanding of the phenomena from the perspectives, experiences, insights, and influences of the participants (Groenewald, 2018). According to Yin (2018), there are five rationales for using the single-case study design rather than the multiple-case study design, which include unusual circumstances, a common case, longitudinal purpose, a critical test of an existing theory, or the case is revelatory in nature. The single case study design was selected because I have access to a specific phenomenon at a unique organization, which was revelatory in nature. Thus, the case study design was appropriate for the study because a key objective of the study is to explore strategies used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Other qualitative designs were explored but not selected for the study included phenomenological, ethnography, and grounded theory. According to Ngenye and Kreps (2020), ethnography, phenomenological, and grounded theory qualitative research designs are recommended for utilization in health communication research studies because of the emphasis on philosophy and science. In the grounded theory research design, participant data are not analyzed to formalize a theory of what, how, and why a phenomenon happened (Ngenye & Kreps, 2020). To the contrary, in the grounded theory design, the researcher analyzes the data as they are collected, and the study protocols are flexible to the adaptation and development of a

theory (Emerson, 2016). Constructing a theory was not the main purpose of the study; therefore, the grounded theory research design was not selected. In the ethnographical research design, entire groups that share a common culture are studied through intensive in-depth observation of interactions, behaviors, and values among group members (Mohajan, 2018). Ethnography was not selected for the study because I was not focused on describing the culture and customs of people. The study of the personal meanings of lived experiences from the perspective of individual participants is the primary interest of the phenomenological research design (Ngenye & Kreps, 2020). The phenomenological research design was not selected for the study because I was not focusing on the personal meanings of individual human experiences.

Research Question

What strategies do Head Start Program leaders use to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

Interview Questions

1. Describe the existing communications environment between program and financial operations at your organization used to increase profitability
2. What business strategies have you implemented to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability?
3. How did the program and fiscal staff respond to the implementation of these business strategies?

4. How did your organization assess the effectiveness of the strategies for increasing communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

5. Based upon your experiences, in what ways did this business strategy increase internal communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

6. What business strategies did you find worked best for improving communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

7. What lessons did you learn from implementing these business strategies?

8. What, if anything, would you have done differently if given an opportunity to develop and implement this or another type of business strategy to increase communications to increase profitability?

9. What additional information would you like to share about business strategies to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

Conceptual Framework

The business process reengineering (BPR) strategy was the conceptual framework I used to identify and understand the strategies used to increase communication between the program and financial operations to increase profitability. Researchers attributed the BPR concept development to Davenport and Short in 1990 (Masayu & Dachyar, 2018). According to Davenport and Short (2003), BPR was developed for companies who found it increasingly necessary to implement business processes that demonstrated more

flexible, communication-based, coordinative, and team-oriented, workplace capability. Radical changes to business systems and processes required the obliteration of old processes to achieve dramatic improvements in organizational performance (Hammer, 1990). Redesigning current business processes with the express intent to substantially improve organizational performance is the primary objective of BPR (Aksyonov et al., 2020). Methodologies for applying the BPR approach require the identification, analysis, and improvement of organizations' key business processes (Ghanadbashi & Ramsin, 2016). Hidayatullah et al. (2024) concluded that the most important action in BPR was the actual redesign of the business process, and the most important approach to the successful implementation of BPR was open communications. Masayu and Dachyar (2018) described the three steps in the BPR method as mapping the as-is, analyzing the as-is, and modeling the to-be processes. According to Belmiro et al. (2000), using the BPR strategy supports and enables partnerships and cross-functionality communications by allowing people to operate beyond their team boundaries, establishing a unified organization-wide vision, and removing demarcation lines of authority. The BPR strategy facilitated my identification and understanding of successful strategies used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability.

Operational Definitions

Business process: A set of logically related tasks performed to achieve a defined business outcome (Davenport & Short, 2003).

Business systems: A set of processes culminating in the way in which a business unit or a collection of units carries out its business (Davenport & Short, 2003).

Organizational citizenship behavior: Voluntary behavior that is beneficial for the organization and co-workers (Li & Janmaat, 2023).

Silo: Clusters of employees lacking communication with other parts of the organization (Vantaggiato et al., 2021).

Assumptions, Limitations, and Delimitations

Assumptions

Research assumptions are defined as widely accepted and reasonable ideas, issues, and positions inherent from the beginning of the study to the final report (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). There were three basic assumptions in the study. The first assumption was that the participants would be able to articulate their experiences either in writing or verbally. The second assumption was that the participants' responses to interview questions would be honest and truthful. The third assumption was that the participants possessed experience with successful communication strategy implementation.

Limitations

Research limitations are described as potential weaknesses beyond the control of the researcher associated with the research design, funding constraints, statistical model constraints, or other factors (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). The validity, generalizability of the results, or implications of the study were the primary limitations of the study. The study had two fundamental limitations. First, Yin (2018) posited that

participants might respond to questions in accordance with what they believe a researcher wants to hear. Second, participants' perceptions about communication strategies were solely dependent upon their experiences within their organizational context, which represented limitations on the extent to which the results of the study were valid for other organizations.

Delimitations

Delimitations are boundaries or limitations specifically imposed and designed by the researcher consciously and intentionally to ensure that the aim of the study is reasonably achievable (Theofanidis & Fountouki, 2018). The study was delimited to a medium-sized Head Start Program located in the Northern Region of the United States. Participants included executives, program managers, and fiscal managers. Participant levels, lengths, and types of experiences varied. Each participant had a responsibility for coordinating and disseminating company communications through internal communication channels.

Significance of the Study

The research findings and recommendations from this study can be used to gain a better understanding of effective communication strategies used to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Functional silos within organizations create barriers that prohibit effective internal communications for improving business processes (Lugo Santiago, 2018). Inefficient internal communication negatively impact overall organizational productivity, culture, profitability, innovation, and efficiency. According to Lugo Santiago (2018), cooperation

is not enough to develop a culture of shared values because only cross-functional and cross-departmental integration of members from different departments' groups could achieve the successful implementation of the collaboration strategy for performance improvement. Improved organizational performance positively impacts both the external and internal stakeholders of an organization.

Internal implications for positive social change included positive impacts to organizational culture, developing a collaborated integrated organization, and improving overall business processes' performance. External implications for positive social change included improvements to external reporting and the provision of a more integrated service model. Santhosh and Baral (2015) posited that enhancing positive attitudes among employees through the promotion of corporate social responsibility activities was a key factor in an organization's success. Strategic communications can be utilized as a catalyst for positive social change in communities (Ciszek, 2017). Therefore, the communities, children, and families receiving the provision of Head Start services could positively benefit from operational efficiencies and improvements in Head Start programs through enhanced integrative customer services resulting from improved internal business processes with concomitant improvements in cross-functional communication.

A Review of the Professional and Academic Literature

Change is an inevitable factor in business. When a problem is identified in the business that affects productivity, competitive advantage, efficiencies, processing, and financial viability, it is the responsibility of the organizational leaders to develop and implement strategies to progress the organization forward through a process of strategic

change. In this literature review, I examined literature wherein researchers posited communication strategies to mitigate functional silos, increase internal communication, or assess and measure the effectiveness of existing internal communication. I discovered three prevalent themes during this literature review, including the importance of the leadership role, the organizational culture's role in sustaining and supporting communication systems, and the need for formalized channels to facilitate communications.

The following tools were used to obtain the literature for this literature review: Walden University's electronic library database, Google Scholar, other online libraries, and websites. BPR was the research lens and conceptual framework used to guide and explore the related theories and concepts in the literature review. I searched a variety of online research databases and local libraries to obtain literature. The literature review included peer-reviewed journal articles, dissertations, and books. A total of 123 references were used to support the literature review section of this study. Eighty-two percent or 101 of the literature review section references are from peer-reviewed sources. Eighty or 65% of the references used to support the literature review section of this study were published within the 2021–2025 period. Regarding the entire study, 247 references were used. Eighty-seven percent or 215 of the references for this doctoral study were peer-reviewed sources. Seventy-three percent or 180 of the references used to support the study were published within the 2021–2025 period. Key terms used for retrieving the electronic sources included *effective management communication*, *leadership communication*, *internal communication*, *business process reengineering*, *organizational*

communication, communication strategies, communication channels, channel expansion theory, business silos, effective communication, effective leadership communication, the star model, siloes, media richness, strategic communication, communication policy, communication theory, communication structure, functional silos, and internal organizational effectiveness.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual frameworks provide the lens for observing a business phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2024). The BPR strategy was selected for the study because redesigning current business processes with the express intent to substantially improve organizational performance is the primary objective of the BPR strategy (Aksyonov et al., 2020). People, technology, strategy, and business process are the four factors of consideration in the BPR approach (Vaez-Alaei et al., 2018). The concepts and principles of BPR had multiple and diverse industry application potential. The integration of BPR and resilience engineering are combined to improve safety and increase optimization in oil firms, which leads to higher efficiencies in the workplace (Vaez-Alaei et al., 2018). Leaders utilized BPR at Indonesian firms to explore how company leaders managed turnaround and their leadership style for implementing BPR (Yulihastri et al., 2018). BPR strategies used in these industries can be applied in the Head Start program to improve communication strategies.

Implementation of BPR resulted in a new management model. The process and concept of reengineering as a set of business processes with the targeted purpose of improving company performance resulted in a fundamentally new management model

(Kyfyak & Lopatynskyi, 2018). According to Wang et al. (2024), BPR radically alters the procedural practices of organizations resulting in reductions to cost and improved business competitiveness. In turn, a new management model resulted in sustainable organization-wide change to the culture and created best practices (Eze et al., 2019). Strategies to successfully transition an organization from functional silos to an integrated enterprise required the use of several practices and efforts to achieve a unified culture.

Other conceptual frameworks reviewed but not selected for the study included the channel expansion theory (CET), communication theory (CT), and the star model. Kashian and Mirzaei (2019) touted that the CET model explains effective communication by way of perceived media richness based on four domains of knowledge-building experience that include perceived competence (experience with the channel), knowledge of content (experience with the messaging topic), organizational culture knowledge (experience with the organizational context), and comfort with interactants (experience with communication co-participants). A user's perception of the media richness of a specific channel of communication depicts their utilization of media as a primary form or source of communication (Mirzaei & Esmailzadeh, 2021). Safdar et al. (2022) summarized CET as a combination of media richness, social influence, and situational factors. CET is primarily used to help managers understand and develop improved strategies for selecting the most effective communication channels (Obinna et al., 2024). Since CET was characterized by a combination of situational factors, social influence, media richness, and is primarily used to select communication channels, it was not

selected as an appropriate research lens to explore internal departmental communication strategies to mitigate silos and improve communications.

The star model, an organizational design model developed by J.R. Galbraith in 1960, posited a five-factor scheme that included strategy, structure, process, people, and rewards (Lemus-Aguilar et al., 2019). The company's strategy is the first organizational design addressed because it connects all the factors and specifies the goals, products, and markets to be served, as well as the way of creating and delivering value to customers and stakeholders (Lemus-Aguilar et al., 2019). Human resources and human capital were addressed in the people and reward factors of the star model. The flow of decision-making information and technology was covered through the process factor, while the hierarchy is established through the structure factor. According to Cordova and Gonzalez (2017), the star model is controllable by organization leaders, and it provides a decision-making framework to catalyst organization design change. The star model connects the five factors of the organizational design and was useful in research studies related to business sustainability and organization design change; but not the overall improvement of internal communication strategies; therefore, it was not selected for this case study.

Shannon (2018) posited that the CT is a concept where messages sent and received influence the reliability of the communication, following the notion that human behavior is connected to the environment. The environment included the past experiences, present circumstances, and future expectations of all parties involved in the transfer of information (Shannon, 2018). Information source, transmitter, receiver, and destination are the four essential elements of the CT. As proposed by French philosopher

Gilbert Simondon in 1958 and 2005, how information is structured and organized must align with how that information is communicated (Bencherki & Iliadis, 2021). CT was primarily useful in research related to employee engagement, business marketing practices, and the study of media influences on human behavior; therefore, CT was not selected as the lens to explore successful communication strategies to mitigate functional silos.

Business Process Reengineering Strategy

BPR complemented with information technology was utilized to drastically improve business process effectiveness and efficiency. Grant and Yeo (2022) touted those businesses using the BPR strategy experienced radically redesigned business processes. BPR was utilized to achieve sustained and dramatic results including improvements in innovation, cost, service, lead time, and quality (Grant & Yeo, 2022). The value added by implementing a BPR approach was sustainable. BPR is a comprehensive solution for streamlining business activities.

A well-defined BPR was required for successful project implementation. To enhance the likelihood of BPR implementation project success, Grant and Yeo (2022) suggested that the BPR must be well defined. Researchers proposed combining BPR with unified modeling language (UML) to eliminate the risk of not having a well-defined BPR (Grant & Yeo, 2022). UML was utilized in combination with BPR to map from the As-Is model to the To-Be model. UML was defined by researchers through a 10-step process that started with the identification of sources of customer dissatisfaction and ended with surfacing assumptions, streamlining, and reengineering the business (Grant & Yeo,

2022). Well-defined BPR reduced the risks of project failure by introducing structure and discipline to the business process.

BPR was utilized to develop competitive business strategies. Al-Shammari (2023) utilized BPR as a significant component to develop a knowledge-enabled customer-centric competitiveness strategy (KCCS). The KCCS model has four pillars that include knowledge management, customer relationship management, competitiveness strategy, and BPR (Al-Shammari, 2023). Al-Shammari proposed that the use of BPR enabled cross-functional coordination and cooperation. Cross-functional coordination and cooperation was frequently noted as a barrier for businesses dealing with customers (Al-Shammari, 2023). BPR was utilized to mitigate the barriers and increase the effectiveness of customer centered competitive strategies.

Organizations in crisis management used BPR to positively impact organization performance and enhance strategic thinking. Researchers found that the use of BPR by the Malaysian electronics manufacturing industry during the coronavirus pandemic had a significant and positive impact on the organizations' performance by advising them to incorporate strategic thinking (Shahul Hameed et al., 2022). Shahul Hameed et al. (2022) purported that the dimensions of BPR, such as top management commitment, information technology capabilities, people management, and organizational readiness for change, had significant positive impacts on organizational performance. Strategic thinking was the moderating variable used by researchers to evaluate the relationship between BPR and the organizations' performance (Shahul Hameed et al., 2022). There were

implications that BPR was used in various industries as the catalyst to improve performance, manage crises, and innovate through strategic thinking.

Several main organizational factors contributed to the successful implementation of BPR. According to Hashem (2020), management commitment, information technology (IT) infrastructure, people management, change readiness, centralization and formalization are the key organizational factors that contribute to the successful implementation of BPR. Hashem (2020) conducted a study of the Egyptian banking sector and concluded that critical enablers to the successful implementation of BPR included an organizational structure with a low degree of formalization coupled with management commitment, IT infrastructure, people management, and change readiness. The Egyptian banking sector has been involved in many major reform efforts since 2004 that included BPR implementation (Hashem, 2020). The main organizational factors affecting the implementation of BPR were used to study an industry in a developing country. Organizations that applied BPR with a focus on the main organization factors increased results for successful implementation of BPR.

The managerial philosophy of BPR properly implemented had the potential to yield positive organizational outcomes. When shareholder interest was the focused primacy of the organization's managers, researchers touted that the managerial philosophy of BPR provided some firms with positive organizational outcomes (Mertens et al., 2024). The primary and intentional focus of managers that implemented BPR was organizational performance and progression (Mertens et al., 2024). According to Mertens et al. (2024), the seven tenets of BPR were intended as a managerial antidote to cure the

negative effects of mediocrity and the traditional corporate structure. The seven tenets of BPR included a focus on outcomes not tasks, identify processes and prioritize redesign, integration of information, centralize geographically dispersed resources, link parallel activities, align decision points with performance and build control in the process, and capture information once at the source (Mertens et al., 2024). Organizations that implemented the seven tenets of BPR experienced progressive improvements in organizational performance and outcomes.

Managers used BPR as a strategic tool for engaging in competitive environments. Modern organizations evoking BPR as a tool to dramatically transform their business processes in a hyper-competitive industry experienced heightened organization-wide performance (Roman & Nelson, 2021). According to Roman and Nelson (2021), implementing the BPR framework assisted organizations with extensively examining deficiencies in current practices that were detrimentally impacting performance. Organizations used BPR to develop strategies for competitive advantage by identifying and correcting practices that negatively impact performance.

BPR was used to improve business processes in many ways. Maximizing quality and minimizing duration, cost, and used resources are purported by Mamrot (2023) as some of the ways that BPR improved business processes. Mamrot used BPR to identify and resolve poor quality and inefficiencies in the law-making process. According to Mamrot, the results of the research indicated that applying BPR to the legislative process positively affected the quality of law-making and the reduction of failures in legislation.

BPR was used to maximize quality, save costs, reduce resources, and minimize processing times.

BPR was used in the hospitality industry to enhance customer service. Chalupa et al. (2021) completed a study using BPR that focused on the improvement of direct telephone sales by the application of a Customer Relationship Management (CRM) system. Researchers found that the application of BPR shortened the CRM system process and allowed front-office staff more time to be customer-oriented (Chalupa et al., 2021). The time efficiencies gained through implementing BPR were used to streamline customer service interactions providing more time for the front office worker to focus on the improvement of customer relations in the hotel industry.

Managers used BPR to evaluate performance. Yang (2022) proposed that BPR should be regarded as a closed input and output system by which a performance appraisal of the organizations' accounting segment with incentive mechanisms could be established. The focus of Yang's research was the supervision and improvement of the accounting departments with poor performance through a ranking process that measured the performance of each process within the unit. Separating the individual accounting processes and measuring them by rank helped managers to identify and pay attention to the areas of poor performance for strategic corrective action which yielded positive organizational performance outcomes (Yang, 2022). Through the implementation of BPR to evaluate performance, managers were able to improve the accounting business processes.

Managers used BPR to identify, improve, and innovate manual business processes. Pasaribu et al. (2021) completed a study of an Indonesian university's system for recording official business trips using BPR. In evaluating the system, researchers found that implementing a solution through BPR that included digitization and multi-unit integration would eliminate the identified obstacles of system inefficiencies, timeliness, human resources, materials, and the lack of effectiveness (Pasaribu et al., 2021). The BPR process implementation conducted by researchers resulted in significant changes to the official trip system from a mixed system of manual/offline and online processes to a completely online system with a decentralized decision process and transparent monitoring systems (Pasaribu et al., 2021). Through the implementation of BPR, managers innovated a manual process that improved processing time, saved paper, reduced costs, and increased efficiency and effectiveness.

Current operation analysis for the purpose of developing improvement strategies was achieved by using BPR. Researchers used the systematic framework of BPR to evaluate and develop strategies for hospital emergency departments to reduce waiting time and balance resource utilization (Srinivas et al., 2021). Researchers found that optimizing the workforce level based on historical demand while adopting a change in the triage process yielded the best performance results by reducing the wait time, reducing the physician workload, reducing cost which balanced the resource utilization, and simplifying the triage process for easier implementation (Srinivas et al., 2021). BPR was used by researchers to resolve emergency room challenges of high demand, limited resources, and waiting time.

The Leadership Role

Leaders must be relationally equipped and keen observers of human behaviors and interactions. Leaders are endowed from birth with natural special characteristics and abilities, which cause them to rise above the circumstances of their surroundings to accomplish and achieve great feats along with their followers (Dziak, 2024).

Leaders develop and apply a specific approach of leadership based on the individual needs of the follower through directive, supportive and relationship behaviors (Bwalya, 2023). A leader's ability to evaluate the following elements is critical to success in the application of this theory; the competence and expertise of the follower, the environmental factors, and the assignment or task (Buzady et al., 2024). Vasilescu (2018) stated that one of the major differences between leaders and managers is that "leaders promote change, new approaches, and work to understand people's beliefs to gain their commitment, managers promote stability, exercise authority, and work to get things accomplished" (p. 172). Based on Vasilescu's statement, the leadership role was more relationship-focused, while the management role is more task oriented. Northouse (2019) adapted the theory from Kotter, which concluded that, "the overriding function of management is to provide order and consistency to organizations, whereas the primary function of leadership is to produce change and movement" (p.12). This theory spoke to the fluidity of the leadership role and the stabilizing components of the management role.

Organization leaders had the responsibility to design, implement, assess, monitor, and oversee internal and external communication strategies. Leaders combine influence and service prioritizing followers through nurturing, empathetic and attentive behaviors

which empowers followers to be high performers (Northouse, 2019). Leaders display high ethics and can be identified through the exhibition of 10 key characteristics, namely: listening, empathy, healing, awareness, persuasion, conceptualization, foresight, stewardship, building community, and commitment to the growth of people (Northouse, 2019). Leaders who exhibited high ethical characteristics empower and influence employees to be high performers.

Organizational communication culture was established top-down in most organizations through the leadership hierarchy. Strong leadership is an essential component of successful business and employee relations (Turaeva, 2023). Leadership and the organizational tone at the top have a major impact on the organization's internal communications, as emphasized by Salman et al. (2023). Follow-up via feedback helped leaders to identify deficiencies and correct errors. According to Satterstrom et al. (2024), ignoring feedback or failing to follow-up regarding communication changes created barriers in communications, and even negative feedback could be used as an opportunity for organizational improvement. Leaders burden the responsibility of creating and ensuring an organizational environment where the flow of information is two-way. Leaders play a critical role in unifying, clarifying, and supporting consistent and open communications between the various levels of management (King et al., 2023). When a leader was successful at creating an environment with free-flowing information, internal communication is supported, encouraged, and become a cultural norm for the organization.

Researchers agreed that organizational leaders play a vital role in the type of communication strategy and the implementation of communications strategies. Stauffer and Maxwell (2020) examined the correlation between leadership and the effective implementation of organizational change. Stauffer and Maxwell provided evidence that sustaining and initiating organization-wide change required effective leadership, and that effective leadership could be used as a strategy or approach to influence organizational change. Okundaye et al. (2019) used the technology acceptance model (TAM) as the conceptual framework to analyze the adoption of information and communication technology strategies by leaders in the target population. Effective leadership drove the selection and implementation of new strategies, which resulted in organization-wide change. Sustaining and initiating successful communications strategies require effective leadership.

As primary decision-makers for the organizations, leaders determined which communications strategies, if any, to adopt and implement in their organizations. A strong positive correlation existed between the attitudes and behaviors of the transformational servant leadership style and both corporate culture and strategies (Stauffer & Maxwell, 2020). Swenson et al. (2019) concluded that there were three themes reflected in the communications strategies of effective leaders, which included process adjustment, alignment, and integration; specifically, communications strategies had to be flexible in adjusting to departmental activities and strategies, then they had to be aligned with other business units within the organization and finally integrated through the organization as a part of the organization-wide goals and priority plan. Adaptive

leadership, which identifies and effectively communicates emergent new collaborative structures rather than focusing on isolation practices, positively contributes to the success of an organization with complex business systems (Powell et al., 2023). Effective leadership styles for influencing corporate culture and strategy implementation were transformational and servant leadership styles. Priority planning and the integration of new communication strategies into organization-wide goals was the responsibility of effective leaders.

A leader's ability to influence and collaborate was sine qua non to the establishment of the organizational culture and the implementation of communication strategies. Lugo Santiago (2018) concluded that collaboration is not an automated process; it is a process of transformation and integration wherein organizational leaders play a critical role in establishing an organizational culture that is conducive to the collaboration strategies. There are seven critical practices to the successful implementation of collaboration strategies posited by the researcher required leaders to develop a roadmap to collaboration that included the creation of a sense of purpose, the creation of a real need for the collaboration, the indoctrination of employees to the culture and values of the organization through on-going training, the sustaining of employees throughout their tenure, the provision of the tools necessary for collaboration, the creation of experiences to positively reinforce desired behaviors, and the development and execution of a well-defined communications strategy (Lugo Santiago, 2018). Yue et al. (2023) concluded that charitable organizations have an added responsibility of public transparency for all of their actions and financial decisions that demand organizational

leaders to implement effective communications strategies both internally and externally. Okundaye et al. (2019) posited that leadership style, organizational culture, and limited resources are factors affecting the decision to adopt information and communication technology strategies. Internal and external collaboration and communication strategies were designed and implemented by the organizations' leaders. Leaders must demonstrate the purpose, need, importance, and provide training reiterating the necessity of departmental collaboration and communication strategies.

Developing strategic plans which addressed potential challenges with the implementation of communication strategies was another duty of effective leaders. Common business challenges to the implementation of strategic plans include poor execution, the lack of resources, ineffective communications, resistance to change, and weak strategies (Palm & Decaux, 2024). Managers at all levels of an organization have the function and responsibility of strategic planning (Steiner, 1979). According to Coccia (2023), the failure of the plan cannot be blamed solely on the execution; there must also have existed some inherent weaknesses/failures in the plan. Communication failures can occur when the plan is too complicated to be understood or remembered (Meng et al., 2024). The lack of resources, time, and funding is traditionally unique to small businesses and non-profit organizations (Godefroid et al., 2024). According to Coccia (2023), obstacles to achieving the plan must be identified and resolved. Strategic planning helped effective leaders to assess, address, and eliminate potential threats to the successful implementation of communication strategies.

Strategic planning is a necessary part of the business process that helps companies to maintain or sustain their competitive advantage in volatily changing markets (Sołoducho-Pelc & Sulich, 2020). If the overall benefit to strategic planning included the longevity of the business, then not having a strategic plan would indicate that a business had shortened its market sustainability. According to Wang et al. (2023), companies utilize business strategies as a guide to success, competitive advantage, and market sustainability. Organizations that fail to use a plan also lose the benefits of increased operational efficiencies, a clearly outlined sense of direction, and are reactive to crisis rather than proactive (Steiner, 1979). The strategic plan was communicated and simplified to ensure company-wide engagement and buy-in.

Organization-wide resistance arose when those responsible for the execution do not fully buy-in to the new vision. Issues like organizational engagement and organizational transformation must be met with the cascading of goals to the departmental level, periodic meetings, and regular conversations about the mission, vision, and goals (Zhongling et al., 2024). Producing the commitment needed to fuel a cycle of ongoing process improvements in the organization requires the engagement of employees through the institutionalization of change management functions (Mehmood & Khattak, 2023). However, to ensure buy-in from leadership and staff, they must commit to its achievement. Authentic leadership styles, effective communications and job satisfaction enhance employee engagement which is critical to the success of the organization (Ramirez-Lozano et al., 2023). Engagement cultivates an organizational culture committed to the achievement and successful implementation of new strategies.

Leaders ensured that communication strategies include a promotion-focused message to successfully engage stakeholders. Stakeholder engagement which included staff, the board of directors, and the management team, coupled with the importance of creating a work environment that was conducive to the sharing of information, was touted as a formula for significant communication practice improvements (Kucukusta et al., 2019). Stakeholder engagement helped to build trusting relationships, which are critical to receiving feedback necessary for improving communication practices, policies, and processes (Kucukusta et al., 2019). Researchers found that the best communication strategy is when the message is framed from a promotion-focused perspective (Lagomarsino et al., 2020). Promotion-focused messages emphasized the benefits of targeted actions and what can be achieved rather than the costs. To promote proactive behaviors, researchers experimented with comparing the effectiveness of prevention-focused versus promotion-focused messages (Lagomarsino et al., 2020). The way the message is framed impacted how the message is received by individuals with high egoistic values.

Business strategy played an essential role in advancing an organization's innovation. Business strategy was used to successfully further innovation in an organization. Styles and Goddard (2014) posited that for an organization to be different, it had to think differently. Change required the application of creativity and a willingness to take some risks. Innovation cannot be limited to products only; the definition of innovation must be broadened to include the implementation of business strategies. According to Styles and Goddard, the last 20 years have produced a new type of hero in

business where inventors of strategy, not products, have emerged. Steiner (1979) posited that long-range planning, which makes current decisions with a futuristic lens, sets the organizational aims through a process of objective/goal development and acts based on future outcomes, is the definition of strategic planning. A well-executed strategic plan will clarify the drivers of the organization, such as the mission and vision; identify any challenges to obtaining the organizational objectives; and help management determine what goals must be achieved to be successful (Sull, 2012).

The steps of the strategic planning process begin with the establishment or analysis of the mission statement (Snyder, 2024). The mission statement provided succinct purpose for the organization's existence. The mission statement should answer the question – why are we here? Once an organization determines why it is in existence, the next step in the strategic planning process is to determine where they are now through a strategic thinking tool called a strength, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) analysis (Puyt et al., 2023). According to Barksdale and Lund (2023), the internal and external data collected and reviewed during the SWOT analysis process are critical to determining the vision of where the organization wants to go.

A clearly articulated and shared vision is the next step in the planning cycle. Once the vision is determined, objectives and goals are created, which layout the organizational directions to transition from the stated mission to an achieved vision (Barksdale & Lund, 2023). Articulating the strategy is the next step, and according to Sull (2012), a strategy's ability to influence action is contingent upon it being remembered, understood, and simple. Goals must be communicated throughout the hierarchy of the organization

ensuring that everyone understands their piece of the plan and accepts ownership for achieving their part (Adelman-Mullally et al., 2023). The final step involved the monitoring of the strategic plan. In this phase of the process, periodic meetings must be held to assess whether goals/objectives are being met and to determine if any adjustments are necessary to the plan (Rajapakshe, 2024). Efficient decision-making processes required the deliberate combination of technology, finances, program operations, inputs, outputs, stakeholders, and all levels of management. Operating in departmental, compartmental, and management silos were no longer conducive to decision-making processes or the achievement of organizational objectives and goals. Organization leaders and managers needed to develop a culture that is convivial to innovation, inclusion, and moderate risks.

Organizational Culture

Northouse (2019) described organizational culture as the norms, values, traditions, and learned beliefs that are common to the group of people who make up the organization. Organizational citizenship behavior is enhanced in organizations where both co-worker communication and supervisor communication satisfaction levels were high (Li & Janmaat, 2023). Organizational culture varied depending on the type of industry and the leaders in that organization. The organizational culture was compared to the thread utilized to make a quilt. The paradox of positive and negative views about organizational change were examined wherein the change is presented as a valuable opportunistic element necessary for corporate development and prosperity; while in contrast change is displayed as an unstable disruption to the organization (“Successful

introduction of workplace,” 2020). The quilt represented the successful outcome or achievement of the organizational goals. When gathering the materials to make a quilt, one collects many different patches of cloth (Thomer & Rayburn, 2024). The patches of cloth were all different textures, shapes, sizes, and colors, similar to the diversification of an organization’s workforce. The thread is used to pull those diverse patches of cloth together to fulfill a common goal or fulfill the common purpose of making a quilt (Arellano, 2022). According to Petitta and Martinez-Corcoles (2023), although the organizational culture was an unconscious informal aspect of the life of the organization, it played a critical role in the success of the organization. When sewn properly, the thread holding the pieces together was unseen but necessary to maintain the integrity of the quilt. Organizational leaders like quilters were very selective in the type of culture that was weaved into an organization’s makeup. According to Abbasi Sani (2024), leaders must be mindful of the tapestry of workplace culture they have actively woven to create the organizational culture. Choosing a thread that was too weak will not last through washing and repeated use. The organizational culture must be practiced and strong enough to withstand the lifecycles of the business without fail (Graziano, 2023). Similarly, the stitching of the thread in the quilt cannot be too loose, likened to an organization that had a written culture but was slack in the full implementation of those values and beliefs.

Leaders had the responsibility of utilizing their influence to positively impact the culture of an organization. Northouse (2019) described ethnocentrism and prejudice as two of the major hindrances to effective leadership. When a leader practices observing

everyone through the lens of their own ethnic, racial, or cultural group, this is defined as ethnocentrism (Northouse, 2019). Leaders had to respect the diversification of the workforce by not inaccurately perceiving or portraying their own values, attitudes, or beliefs as if they were better than that of another. Prejudice involves strong beliefs, false generalizations, and judgments against or about a group that is usually based on previous experience, false data, or misconceptions (Northouse, 2019). Leaders had to ensure that they guard against the practice of both ethnocentrism and prejudice because they prohibit the leaders' ability to comprehend and value all of the people in their workforce.

Establishing, stabilizing, and maintaining the culture of the organization was a role of leadership. The traditional idea of top-down, expert, and supervisor-driven change has many disadvantages (Schultz, 2014). Inclusion and buy-in from both management and staff were critical to the success of any organization-wide change. The practice of engaging staff and managers at all levels in the process of change was practiced as a part of the organizational culture. When organizations create a supportive environment that values the perspectives of its employees, this creates a culture where the organization can utilize the human capital knowledge to make data informed decisions which lead to better outcomes, job satisfaction, and improved performance (Magon & Caruso, 2023).

Employee engagement was critical to sustaining organizational culture change. Meaningful internal communications mediated through employee engagement positively influenced the enactment of employee strategic behaviors (Arif et al., 2023). One of the most valuable aspects of strengthening the relationship between the employee and the organization is internal communications (Santoso et al., 2023). Businesses that choose an

engaged, dynamic approach typically have a positive response to the changes since employees are more open-minded to changes where their input was taken into consideration (“Successful introduction of workplace,” 2020). Neill and Jiang (2017) indicated that a primary reason to address internal communications strategically was to align corporate culture, motivate employees by facilitating engagement and commitment, to communicate organizational change, increase profitability, improve productivity, and support the exchange of data or information critical to the decision-making process. Potosky and Azan (2023) posited that to change the attitude and behaviors of thousands, the critical component necessary to strategically implement and sustain change required a shift in the organizational dynamics and culture. Okundaye et al. (2019) reported that the positive benefits of adopting information and communication technology strategies include increased productivity, improved efficiency, financial benefits, greater accountability, improved communications, and job creation.

Adaptability and flexibility in the communication of organization-wide change was essential to the successful implementation of organizational culture change. Swenson et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of adjusting, aligning, and integrating communications strategies to achieve organizational synergy. Synergetic results are produced when an organization exhibits an organizational climate with superior levels of communication and high levels of staff cohesion (Pandit et al., 2018). Change communicated effectively through transparency yielded positive effects on the company’s culture transformation process (“Successful introduction of workplace,” 2020). According to Jeske and Olson (2025), organizations that practice functional silos

experienced internal communication barriers and concerns that negatively impacted organizational culture. In Neill and Jiang's (2017) case study, encroachment is examined from the lens of both functional and structural; wherein, functional encroachment occurs when a department intrudes on the activities or domain of another department, while structural encroachment is the assignment of someone from outside a department's discipline to manage the department. Both forms of encroachment act to prohibit and interfere with the policy decision influence of a department (Neill & Jiang, 2017).

A coordinated collaborative communications strategy supported the successful implementation of communication strategies across business systems. Lugo Santiago (2018) presented research on seven practices utilized to strategically implement a collaboration strategy to successfully transition an organization from functional silos to an integrated enterprise. Efforts to achieve a unified culture and a collaborated integrated organization included the implementation of over 50 business process re-engineering events; however, Lugo Santiago revealed that cooperation was not enough to develop a culture of shared values because only cross-functional and cross-departmental integration of members and tribal groups could achieve successful implementation of the collaboration strategy.

The inevitability of change itself provided a source of stability in organizations where creativity and innovation thrive. In these types of organizations, change is the stable continuum constantly thrusting the organization forward, causing it to grow, maintain its relevance, and ultimately resulting in an adaptive organization on a continuous cycle of process improvement (Aalders, 2023). General Mills Canada

capitalized on the value of implementing a business strategy process. Due to concerns that the company's success had plateaued in 2010 and driven by the belief that enabling employees to become more innovative would boost company performance over the next few years, President David P. Homer met with his senior management team to discuss the company's strategic plans for 2011 (Mark & Mitchell, 2014).

Creating a culture conducive to innovation was the first strategy implemented by General Mills Canada in its efforts to improve performance through innovation. When intense competition exists in the market, innovation is more than just products; innovation must be the life source of the organization, which could only be achieved by creating a stronger company culture of innovation (Mark & Mitchell, 2014). Since the inevitability of change is an infinite constant, embracing the highs, lows, and flows of transition should be the logical response to implementing change in organizations (Hubbart, 2023). Smith et al. (2020) argued and advocated for an integrated multi-philosophy approach to organizational change because of the interdependent relationship of continuity and change evident in organizations that implement change successfully. For many organizations, change was a necessary logical progression expected in the cycle of continuous growth through the process of improvement; while other organizations suffered through the dynamics of organizational change and failed to achieve the transformation.

According to Dyer et al. (2016), there are eight steps or tasks key to successful change implementation, which includes the generation of a sense of urgency, building a coalition, creating a vision, communicating the vision, the empowerment individuals who

will be responsible for acting, the acknowledgment of short-term wins, maintaining and driving forward momentum, and finally, the institutionalization of the change. Achieving the perfect alignment or line of sight from vision to culture change is complex, requires flexibility to make adjustments as needed over a period of time, and requires consistently deliberate monitoring practices (Pettit et al., 2023). Communication strategies that were effective and worked well with one organization's culture may not be as effective in another organization. Clear communications of strategic objectives and goals are the organizational mechanism used to enhance and drive the alignment of company-wide actions and behaviors (Jerab, 2024).

Communication was sine qua non to developing, maintaining, and sustaining relationships both internally and externally. Communications are inherent in the decision-making process, the coordination of activities to achieve goals, problem-solving activities, and throughout the change management processes (Idogawa et al., 2023). Communication and engagement were two elements critical to successful organizational change. The frequency, method, and transparency of effective communications during change are the discriminating factors that determine whether an organizational change is perceived as having a positive or negative impact (Mumtaz et al., 2024).

Engagement of all staff and managers at all levels affected by the organizational change created the atmosphere of buy-in, responsibility, and accountability wherein those who are engaged own the success or failure of the organizational change. The manner in which the organizational change is communicated, and the level of employee engagement are two reasons why some organizations experienced successful organizational change

while others did not (Mutha & Srivastava, 2023). The most difficult organizational changes to implement are divergent organizational changes (Skrynnyk, 2023). Divergent organizational changes are defined as out-of-the-box, abnormal, or non-institutional status quo changes (Skrynnyk, 2023). However, a change agent's relational abilities to influence, persuade, and effectively communicate were critical to the successful implementation of a new vision or change within the organization. Skrynnyk (2023) concluded that a direct correlation existed between the adoption of changes within an organization and the network of relationships created by the change agent prior to the implementation of a divergent change.

Responsibility for change must be given or taken because we no longer live in a society of "do as I say, because I say so" (Pepinsky, 2018, p. 33). Effective communication of the who, what, where, when, how, and most importantly, the why of a change significantly contributed to the success of an organizational change. The balance between autonomy and control must be aligned with an organization's culture, goals, values, and strategies (Beretta & Smith, 2023). Failure to align and balance these factors led to failures in the successful implementation of organizational change. According to Bailey and Lumpkin (2023), the key to mitigating this risk of failure is to engage all stakeholders. This participatory design involves everyone in the initial creation and systematic process of improvement (Schmidt, 2023).

Engaging employees through the institutionalization of change management functions produces the commitment needed to fuel a cycle of ongoing process improvements in the organization (Baculio & Java, 2024). The holistic and inclusive

view of the systems philosophy, along with the humanistic approach of the psychological philosophy, supported the two reasons for successful organizational change. In the psychological philosophy of change, the person or individual is the primary focal point of the change (Graetz & Smith, 2010).

The relational nature of both effective communications and employee engagement did fit the individual change aspect of psychological philosophy. Because of the systematic domino effect inherent in organization-wide change, successful organizational change management must be implemented across a range of systems (Cheng et al., 2024). The strategic application of both effective communications and the engagement of stakeholders across systems within the organization were necessary steps to achieving the transformation, which aligns directly with the systems philosophy of change. Organizational change was a non-linear process. The deployment of multiple philosophies in the process of organizational change increased the chances of successful implementation and transformation.

Formalized Communications Channels

There was a consensus among researchers that organizations that lacked formalized communications plans, channels, and communications departments benefited both internally and externally from implementing formalized communications strategies. Ineffective internal communications strategies can lead to catastrophic organizational outcomes (Zara et al., 2023). Specifically, investigators discussed the linkages of miscommunications in the trauma setting to fatal errors, medical mishaps, and decreases in patient care (Raley et al., 2017). Miscommunication accounted for 67% of the

preventable deaths among trauma patients and was cited as a significant contributing factor to 70 medical mishaps in the study; therefore, effective team communication is a critical component in trauma departments (Raley et al., 2017). The lack of communication training for trauma teams was identified as the primary reason for the trauma team's ineffective communications. Murphy and Campbell (2017) examined strategies that assessed the effectiveness of internal communications channels used by leaders and posited three themes for the development of communication strategies, which included informal assessment strategies, indirect assessment strategies, and efficient versus timely assessments.

It was important to identify both effective and ineffective internal communication channels. Kim et al. (2019) touted that a relational context exists between employee responses and the organization's internal communication strategies. Positive and negative employee responses were linked to the organization's ability to effectively communicate during the crisis (Monternel et al., 2023). Specifically, the communications components of timing strategy and message strategy were contributing factors to employee emotional receptiveness and employee support behaviors (Kim et al., 2019). The conceptual framework utilized in Murphy and Campbell's (2017) case study was the channel expansion theory, which researchers used to highlight the implication of the plethora of new communications channels to message content. Since information and communications technology is the primary conduit for facilitating strategic planning, formulating, sharing and planning future research, forecasting process efficiencies and effectiveness, and enhancing decision-making, Okundaye et al. (2019) concluded that it is

a primary factor contributing to increased innovation, competitive advantages and overall success of the enterprise. Neill and Jiang (2017) posited that true collaborations of shared ideas, resources, and open exchanges of information would require an organization-wide culture change, a primary source or system to channel organizational communications, and support from the organization's leaders.

It was important for organizations to manage internal communications through strategic planning. Researchers conducted a case study of a state-owned sugar production agribusiness, which implemented an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system that consists of five project components (Darmaningrat et al., 2019). The success of the five projects required planners to effectively manage communications through a communication management plan which incorporated stakeholder needs and considered the suitability of the project communication activities. Ineffective communications were identified by researchers as a risk to the success of the project, which could lead to project failure (Darmaningrat et al., 2019). To mitigate the inherent risk of ineffective communications, researchers posited that the communication management plan should include regularly scheduled and documented meetings, disclosures of problems with updated resolutions, project status reporting, and multiple mediums of communication such as emails and texts (Darmaningrat et al., 2019). Identification and management of internal communications was a critical contributing factor to the successful implementation of the ERP project of the sugar production company (Darmaningrat et al., 2019).

Multiple communication tools or means of communicating were a major theme identified by organizations that have successful internal communication strategies. Organizations who engaged in diverse methods and ranges of strategic communications achieved positive results with both internal and external communications (Macnamara, 2021). Interviewees provided several means of communication, which included frequent team meetings, board meetings, emails, monthly reports, text, phone calls, face-to-face interactions, written policies and procedures, and invoice logs (Shanga et al., 2017). According to Shanga et al. (2017), the use of multiple communication tools such as checklists, training, evaluations, and electronic assessments improved internal communications. Researchers recommend that firms consider the simultaneous development of formal communication plans along with the assessment tool to measure the efficiency of the communication channels (Murphy & Campbell, 2017). Glaeser and Lang (2024) highlighted the benefits of utilizing the links of finance, innovation, and strategy to transform an organization from counting outputs to tracking outcomes. In an age of transparency and accountability, financial managers must learn to adapt their reporting from a siloed approach to one that implores strategy and innovation to communicate financial data (Chittimineni et al., 2024).

Organizational silence and silos increased the risk of communication failures in organizations. Vantaggiato et al. (2021) operationally defined a silo as a cluster of employees lacking communications with other parts of the organization. Organizational silence negatively impacted job performance and job satisfaction (Kılıç et al., 2021). According to Connair (2013), department-wide versus agency-wide management of

organizational risks generated silo management of risks which presented a deterrence to an agency's ability to see the big picture. Connair posited that the implementation of an integrated Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) would eliminate the silo management of risks within organizations that were preventing organizations from achieving their objectives. An event that prevents an organization from accomplishing its objectives was defined by Connair as organization risks. Connair questioned, what happens when a risk doesn't belong to a specific department? Connair posited that no one takes responsibility for the management of the risks when it does not belong to a specific unit; therefore, the risks are undermanaged, and results can be devastating to the organization as a whole. Connair concluded in his findings that the integrated approach rather than a compartmentalized approach to managing organizational risks achieved the overall best outcomes. In fact, organizations that utilized and implemented the innovative system of ERM thrived when faced with threats instead of just surviving.

The lack of effective strategies to increase communications between program and financial operations created business silos that prevented effective business operations. Breaking silos through shared communications supported organizations by increasing the guarantee of control stability in business communication system (Mahfouzi et al., 2021). According to Czachorowski et al. (2023), lowering overall business costs and creating flexibility in operations requires the removal of silos and the increased use of conventional systems. When a specific business department, sector, or group does not share information with others in the same organization, this is known in the business community as a silo mentality (Werhane, 2023). According to Werhane (2023), the silo

mentality resulted in a reduction in business operational efficiencies, negatively impacts employee morale, and increased the potential demise of the production culture of the business. Business silos are created when the organizational structure is built upon a foundational approach of divide and conquer (Lepore et al., 2023).

Communication strategies that empowered employees mitigate the negative impacts of human asset specificity and the performance ambiguity triggered by functional silos. Dalal et al. (2023) concluded that an employee's commitment to the organization was directly linked to the employee's satisfaction with the organization's communication. Researchers used the transaction cost theory from an exchange perspective to examine and explain why firms adopt empowerment practices and how firm performance is affected by the adoption (Yin et al., 2019). Yin et al. (2019) theorized that the two major characteristics of the employer-employee exchange that shape the firm's decision to adopt empowerment practices are human asset specificity and performance ambiguity. Leveraging human resources for competitive advantage and enhanced organizational performance was posited as the primary purpose or goal for applying and adopting empowerment practices (Yin et al., 2019). The transfer of power through high levels of autonomy and control to individual employees with respect to their body of work was defined as the empowerment strategy. Researchers concluded that empowerment practices could be utilized to mitigate the negative impacts of human asset specificity and performance ambiguity on a firm's performance (Yin et al., 2019). Disciplinary silos were not an excuse for limiting the empowerment practices that facilitate the integration of an organization's communication channels.

Empowered employees utilize competencies like communication, interpersonal, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills to broaden communications beyond the disciplinary silo. According to Nisula and Pekkola (2018), narrow-focused communication strategies created disciplinary silos; however, an integrated system was posited as the solution to break the silos. The holistic approach incorporated learning communities, structured intellectual coherence, and hands-on training through an enterprise resource planning supported learning environment (Nisula & Pekkola, 2018). Solutions for transitioning from the siloed approach to a model that is more holistic included a framework of three activities essential to the elimination of the silos: sensing, seizing, and transforming (Nisula & Pekkola, 2018). Disciplinary silos were defined as excessive compartmentalization. Communication between business units and business innovation were stifled in environments where disciplinary silos exist.

Organizations had to be committed to maintaining their information and communication technology (ICT) to remain relevant and positively contribute to the societal transformation of their perspective communities. The transformative effects of ICT were described as pivotal in changing how people and businesses interact, live, and work globally (Albion & Tondeur, 2018). Pivotal changes included the way people access information, the means for interactions, and technological tools for engaging, such as computers, laptops, tablets, and smartphones. Albion and Tondeur (2018) concluded with concerns that organizations were not transforming at the same rate as ICT and touted the importance of coupling the strategy and ICT to effectively implement and maintain the positive transformational changes in society. Due to the evolving dynamics of society

and technology, the means for delivering high-quality, accurate, and precise information both internally and externally had to be appropriate to the demand.

Internal and external communication was facilitated through the organization's website. Aripin et al. (2023) examined the communications process and strategies that supported an organization's involvement in and managing social issues. Communications strategies and digital media affect social issues management by engaging stakeholders and potentially enhancing a firm's contribution to positive social change in their community (Bailey & Lumpkin, 2023). Communication teams utilized the company website to reinforce its commitment to inclusivity. Researchers concluded that the digital communications environment facilitated the engagement of stakeholders (Aripin et al., 2023). Modifications had to be made to communication management practices to ensure they include a component for responding to social issues internally and externally.

Implementation of communication strategies was an effective and viable tool for eliminating siloes. Chen (2024) discussed the utilization of communications as a tool to eliminate siloes in the tourism industry. The purpose of the study was to develop sustainable partnerships with untraditional stakeholders. Engagement through communications facilitated the adoption of broader networks, the development of reciprocal capacities for learning, and the creation of inclusive, sustainable partnerships (Cockburn-Wootten & McIntosh, 2024). Transformational change in the tourism industry was heavily dependent upon the organization's ability to establish long-term relationships. Partnership development was sine qua non to address the issues of economic disadvantage and social exclusion.

In a crisis, newer types of formal communication strategies were implemented to engage internal and external stakeholders. Electronic discussion facilitated through video conferencing and social media significantly enhanced communication efforts. Summerer (2020) discussed the collaborative electronic communications environment created by physicians as a result of the global pandemic. The “perfect storm” created by the crisis paved the way for the execution of innovative business communication strategies that included a heavy reliance on video conferencing as a primary means of communication (Summerer, 2020). Organizations that shifted to more innovative communication strategies during the crisis experienced organization-wide communication success.

The implementation of communication strategies was an effective and viable tool for impacting perceptions. Dorrance Hall and Scharp (2018) explored successful college student transitions from a communications perspective through the lens of the family communication pattern theory (FCP). The FCP model was used by researchers to understand the transitional challenges and suggest communication interventions. In the FCP model, the influence of communication apprehension and family communication patterns are examined to determine their impact on students’ transition perspectives (Dorrance Hall & Scharp, 2018). Two thousand two hundred fifty-two college students were surveyed about their transition to college (Dorrance Hall & Scharp, 2018). Dorrance Hall and Scharp concluded that more positive perceptions resulted when conformity orientation and conversation orientation were present. Lower communication apprehension was associated with conversation orientation. Practical implications were touted by researchers for the development of communications strategies that could be

used by college retention specialists, educators, parents, and students to positively impact perceptions and ensure successful transitions (Dorrance Hall & Scharp, 2018). The successful execution of communication strategies that included communication interventions positively impacted employee perception.

Literature Review Conclusion

Strategies existed to enhance and improve internal business communications. Organizational leaders played a vital role in driving internal communication strategies that translate into and transform the organizational culture. Organizations experiencing functional silos or ineffective internal communications should consider developing written internal communication policies and exercising effective communication strategies to improve organizational communication deficiencies. Head Start programs are not the only industry affected by the devastating effects of business silos. Gillani et al. (2024) identified the limitations created by business silos in digital technology organizations. Silos do not support the digital systems and the integration of services, which requires a coordinated effort across multiple business areas within the organization (Gillani et al., 2024). Organizations that switched to the team-based decision-making processes required cooperation and the coordination of multiple departments. Researchers posited that increasing networking and collaboration between teams mitigated silos and helped organizations overcome communication barriers (Favarin et al., 2024). Business leaders must seek out strategies to increase organizational communications and eliminate the adverse effects of business silos. Strategies driven by the organization's leadership that implemented organizational culture changes through formalized communications

channels significantly improved an organization's success rate by eliminating and mitigating communication silos.

Transition

The study of leadership strategies to increase internal communications provided leaders with proven strategies to mitigate communication failures in their organizations. Strategies existed to enhance and improve internal business communications. Functional silos within organizations created barriers that prohibited effective internal communications. The existing body of literature for successful communication strategies to mitigate functional silos, increase internal communications, or assess and measure the effectiveness of existing internal communications varied. The three prevalent themes during this literature review included the importance of the leadership role, the organizational culture role in sustaining and supporting communication systems, and the need for formalized channels to facilitate communications. Researchers who explored successful communication strategies offered that organizational leaders play a vital role in driving internal communication strategies that translate into and transform the organizational culture. My analysis of the literature review findings revealed that strategies driven by the organization's leadership that implemented organizational culture changes through formalized communications channels significantly improved an organization's success rate by eliminating and mitigating communication silos. This review of professional and academic literature included articles related to the topic of communication strategies as drivers for the successful elimination and mitigation of communication siloes. Section 2 included a comprehensive depiction of the research

methodology and design, population and sampling, data collection instruments and techniques used in the research study. In addition, this section included a comprehensive discussion on participants, the role of the researcher, data collection and organization techniques, data analysis, reliability, and validity.

Section 2: The Project

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this qualitative single case study was to explore strategies used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. The target population consisted of four leaders from one Head Start Program in the Northern Region of the United States with multiple service locations who had demonstrated success in implementing strategies that increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability.

Role of the Researcher

Gaining access to a group of study participants, developing a dialog, organizing the research process, executing the research, collecting the data, and analyzing the results is the primary role of the researcher in data collection (Tracy, 2024). I controlled all phases of the study as the primary research instrument. The primary research instrument role includes concept definition, multiple-source data collection, completed interviews, transcribed interviews, data analyses, and development of codes and themes, as described by several researchers (Sanjari et al., 2014). I served as the primary instrument for data collection in this case study.

As suggested by Yin (2018), researchers use various sources of data including semistructured interviews and organizational documents. I reviewed organizational documents and conducted semistructured interviews to collect data from various sources for the study. I collaborated with leaders of the industry group to develop a recommended list of qualified potential participants from which to selectively invite candidates.

Collecting accurate data, conducting participant interviews, and analyzing data is the primary role of the researcher. Groenewald (2018) stressed the importance of researchers' ability to actively listen, acknowledge and respect the views of the participant, and apply attention to the details with accountability for the integrity of the recorded responses. I conducted semistructured interviews using the telephone with audio recordings to collect data for my research. I was responsible for transcribing notes from each interview, evaluating and analyzing the data collected, and compiling the results.

My connection with communications strategies originated in 2007 with my role as a Director of Finance, spanning my career to 2023 for several Head Start Programs in South Carolina, Florida, Maryland, and Virginia. I have had direct experience with the communication challenges between program and financial operations in Head Start organizations. My prior experience as Director of Finance for 17 years allows me to have a realistic perspective of a wide gamut of programmatic and fiscal communications challenges in Head Start programs. Working with industry members in Head Start broadened my world view to include a wide variety of business challenges and scenarios. My experience helped me to develop interview questions adept of uncovering the phenomena that could explain the varied experiences of participants. Familiarity with the business problem and organization members also helped me in assembling a qualified, purposeful sample population of participants willing to share experiences and confidential data.

When conducting social research, ethical considerations that researchers should take into account are readily available in the form of guidelines, codes, and regulations

enforced by professional associations and review boards (Head, 2020). Researchers are under a moral obligation to conduct their research in an ethical manner (Head, 2020), and in line with the guidelines provided by *The Belmont Report* protocol (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979). The National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research (1979) published *The Belmont Report*. *The Belmont Report* established basic ethical principles and guidelines for researchers by addressing the ethical issues arising from conducting research with human subjects. The three basic ethical principles include respect for persons, beneficence, and justice (McMillan et al., 2022).

Respect for persons, beneficence, and justice are the three basic ethical principles of research involving humans (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979). Acknowledging participants' autonomy, recognizing that some participants may have diminished autonomy, and then acting accordingly is an example of a researcher who is applying the *respect for persons* principle (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979). When honoring the *beneficence* principle, researchers agree to bring no harm to participants while maximizing benefits (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979). Compliance with the *justice* principle requires researchers to treat participants fairly, which is related to the potential benefits and burdens brought by conducting the research

(National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979).

Information on the application of ethical principles is included in *The Belmont Report* protocol. The protocol includes the application of principles related to the securement of informed consent, assessment of risks and benefits, and selection of subjects. The section on informed consent specifies the disclosure of information, the comprehension of such information, and the voluntariness of participation (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979). Conformity to (a) the ethical principles of *The Belmont Report* protocol, (b) any requirements of their Institutional Review Board (IRB), and (c) any additional ethical requirements of the participating organization is my responsibility as the researcher.

I explored strategies that Head Start Program leaders utilized to improve organizational performance and increase communication between program and financial operations. Each participant was emailed a consent form prior to their telephone interview. Each participant in the study was asked to sign a consent form and return it via email to voluntarily participate in the study. Each participant was treated in an ethical manner. Research was conducted in accordance with *The Belmont Report's* protocol and Walden University's IRB requirements. The IRB is responsible for ensuring that all Walden University research complies with the University's ethical standards as well as U.S. federal regulations. IRB approval is required when research involves the collection or analysis of data from human subjects. The primary purpose of an IRB is to protect the

interests of human subjects. IRB approval was obtained before the collection of any data, including data derived from a pilot study. I did not commence with the research study before obtaining the required permission from the IRB of Walden University. I explained the *informed consent* principle to participants and acquired participants' signed consent forms before conducting my research to ensure the ethicality of the research study. I allowed participants to withdraw at any stage of the study, treated all participants fairly, reminded participants that participation is voluntary, and ensured confidentiality of information.

Avoiding bias in the research process is difficult because researchers may be inclined to favor evidence supporting their underlying beliefs (Coleman, 2022). Based on my experience as a Head Start Program Director of Finance, I managed bias by defocusing and opening my mind to new experiences and situations prior to conducting research. I maintained a heightened sense of self-awareness to monitor my personal subjectivity to mitigate potential biases before they affected the study by avoiding research topics that are of personal significance to me. To avoid bias, researchers include member checking or transcript review in their research design (Coleman, 2022). Using member checking affords participants an opportunity to review the researcher's description of the participant's experiences (Coleman, 2022).

I conducted member checking by giving participants my written interpretations of their responses to interview questions and asking participants to verify that my interpretations of their answers are accurate. Through the meticulous recording of the assumptions and limitations of the study, I provided the reader with information to

evaluate reliability and validity of the study. A research journal was used as my personal lens as well as a method for managing bias. My process for managing and mitigating my personal bias during data collection and analysis was demonstrated by using an interview protocol, member checking, and reaching data saturation. Data saturation in qualitative research is achieved when the researcher has reached a full understanding of the participants' perspective (Saunders et al., 2018). When there is no new information, coding, or themes inherent in the research, and the research results can be replicated, data saturation will be achieved (Fusch & Ness, 2015). I reached data saturation in this study when I had a full understanding of the participants' perspectives, there was no new information inherent in the research, and the results can be replicated.

An interview protocol includes information such as interview procedures, a script of the introduction and the conclusion, prompts for obtaining consent from participants, and interview questions and prompts (Roberts, 2020). I shared the consent form with all participants. I used an interview protocol (see Appendix B) to assist and guide me through the interview process and to ensure that I consistently shared the same information with all participants. I used the interview questions (see Appendix A) to ensure that each participant is asked the same question. I used the script described in Appendix B of the interview protocol to ensure that each participant received the same introduction and conclusion during the interview process.

I reviewed organizational documents and analyzed performance outcomes. In case study research, the review of organizational documents can be used to gain an understanding of the company's history. The combination of interviews and document

analysis are used by researchers to collect appropriate data in support of addressing the conceptual framework and research questions. Ethical research practices require that interviews be conducted to ensure the protection of participants without endangering the quality of the research (Taquette & Borges da Matta Souza, 2022).

Garrels et al., (2022) noted that the practicality and significance of in-depth interviews as a method for collecting rich narrative data adds value to qualitative research because participants often share comprehensive information related to their lived experiences. Jameson (2017) supported this idea by stating that conducting semistructured interviews is the best interview method to use in qualitative research because the type of data collected from this interview method cannot be obtained using structured questionnaires, participant observation, or an analysis of the literature. Participant interviews give qualitative researchers the opportunity to gather comprehensive data from participants rather than using surveys for data collection. Researchers collect interview data via written transcriptions, audio recordings, and visual drawings, which add context to the richness of the data collected and provide additional tools for analyzing and disseminating findings (Jellema et al., 2023).

Participants

I used purposive sampling to recruit four participants who were leaders from one Head Start Program located in the Northern Region of the United States with multiple service locations. Potential participants must be knowledgeable about the phenomenon under study (Khoa et al., 2023). Participants selected in the study participated in a voluntary interview. To be eligible for participation in the study, the participant (a) must

had been a past or present full-time employee for at least 2 years in a mid-level manager or senior executive role and (b) must have participated in the implementation of communication strategies to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability.

Researchers used recruitment strategies that included social media, surveys, direct invitation, and poster distribution to gain access to research participants (Bredal et al., 2024). Direct email invitations were used to gain organizational access to participants. I reached out to the Head Start Director of the program via phone call to discuss the case study. I sent a copy of the consent form and Interview Questions (Appendix A) via email to the designated authorized organizational approver for permission to access participants. Once organizational approval was obtained, I contacted participants via email and followed up with a recruitment letter that gave a brief overview of the case study. Building a bridge between the participant and the researcher requires a collaborative process of sharing knowledge and experiences that will ultimately benefit everyone involved (Ehsan, 2024). Results of the case study will be shared with the participants and the organization.

Gaining trust is a slow process; however, positive relationships can be built over time (Ehsan, 2024). To establish a working relationship with participants, I shared my industry experiences with them, discussed the potential positive outcomes of the study, and reminded them of my responsibility to maintain the confidentiality of the study participants. According to Bredal et al. (2024), the participants' story is validated by providing a form of interest free interaction that highlights how much the participants'

life and experience matter. In the pre-interview conversation with participants, I emphasized how important understanding the participants' lived experiences is to gaining an understanding of the phenomenon.

A video conference was scheduled with each participant via Zoom or Microsoft Teams. Research questions were forwarded to participants 2-5 business days prior to the scheduled interview. Permission was obtained from each participant to audio record the interview via Zoom or Microsoft Teams. Telephone interviews were arranged for participants with video conferencing challenges. Telephone interviews were recorded using an audio-recording device. One-on-one semistructured interviews were conducted with each participant. Karunarathna et al. (2024) touted that to obtain quality responses, data collected from participants must include their shared experiences and thoughts.

Researchers established enrollment goals to ensure the recruitment of diversified participants whose characteristics align with the research topic (Cullen et al., 2023). The participant eligibility criteria were used to establish the recruitment criteria for potential participants in the study. I intentionally engaged with participants whose characteristics align with the overarching research question. Participant eligibility criteria were designed to target participants whose experiences align with the phenomenon under study. According to Gallegos et al. (2023), a researcher risks diminishing the applicability and impact of research finding to local contexts when they fail to engage with intended participants and achieve representativeness.

Research Method and Design

Research Method

The research method selected for the study was the qualitative method. Researchers use the qualitative method because this method best captures the experience of participants using semistructured interviews with open-ended and follow-up questions (Thompson, 2023). I used the qualitative method to best capture the experience of participants using semistructured interviews with open-ended questions. Participants were interviewed to record their lived experiences of successful strategies to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability; therefore, the qualitative research method was the best research method to conduct the study.

The quantitative research method was not selected for the study. Thompson (2023) revealed the limitations of quantitative research surveys due to the potential to misrepresent participants' judgments. Quantitative research is a meaning-related endeavor that provides a systematic approach to a phenomenon for discovering embedded relationships between specific variables (Franz, 2023). Although case study research data is not inherently quantitative, it can come in the form of words, images, tones, gestures, and impressions that capture the essence of the reality of why an anomaly occurred, not necessarily a relationship (Nikmanesh & Mohd Nor, 2019). Causality and the relationships between variables were not the focus of the study; therefore, the quantitative research method was not optimal for exploring successful communication strategies.

Matović and Ovesni (2023) described the mixed methods as an integrative combination that utilizes the interaction between qualitative and quantitative research methods to explain a phenomenon. In the mixed method, the integration of the two methods is primarily associated with the results, findings, and interpretations, which are the later stages of the research process (Matović & Ovesni, 2023). Triangulation, complementarity, development, initiation, and expansion are the five reasons for selecting the mixed research method (Matović & Ovesni, 2023). Because I do not need the quantitative part of the mixed methods approach, I did not select it for the study.

Research Design

The case study design was selected for the study. In the case study research design, researchers create a space for the voice of the participants to gain an understanding of the phenomena from the perspective, experience, insight, and influence of the participant (Groenewald, 2018). I selected the case study design because my goal was to obtain an understanding of the phenomenon under study from the perspective, experience, insight, and influence of the participants in the study. According to Jones-Hooker and Tyndall (2023), case studies are often used to gain an in-depth understanding of phenomena from a real-world context while overlooking the cultural context of the phenomena. Thus, the case study design was appropriate for the study because a key objective of the study was to understand the strategies used by leader participants to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability.

The single case study design was selected for the study rather than the multiple case study design due to limitations related to access and availability. According to Yin (2018), multiple case studies and single case studies are the same research design; however, the multiple case study includes two or more cases to explore the same phenomena. I did not have knowledge of or access to another Head Start agency who used strategies to successfully increase communications and mitigate siloes between fiscal and program operations. Other qualitative designs explored but not selected for the study included phenomenological, ethnography, and grounded theory.

The grounded theory is a systematic qualitative research design method where data is collected, analyzed, and categorized to formulate concepts, theories, and or identify relationships about group behaviors, social processes, and norms (Díaz et al., 2023). The grounded theory was not selected because I was not seeking to formulate a theory about communication strategies. Ethnography focuses on the study of customs and cultures for individuals and groups (Chatterjee, 2023). Researchers use the ethnographical design to focus on the cultural context of values, beliefs, customs, and traditions influencing the phenomena (Jones-Hooker & Tyndall, 2023). Ethnographical approaches to research focused on the environmental places and spaces impacting the phenomena (Dahl & Tjora, 2023). The ethnographic qualitative research design was not selected for this case study because of the focus on the cultural context. The phenomenological qualitative research design focused on the meaning of lived experiences of the research participants (Bouzioti, 2023). Researchers gained insight about the phenomena from the hermeneutic phenomenology study of participants' lived

experiences (Barrett-Rodger et al., 2023). The hermeneutics are related to the interpretations and perspectives of the participants who experienced the phenomena. A descriptive phenomenological study design involves the identification of significant statements, the formulation of exhaustive descriptions and the extraction of meanings about the phenomenon through the lived experiences of research participants (Alhalabi et al., 2023). Because this case study focused on the exploration of successful strategies, the phenomenological research design, which focuses on the meaning of participants' lived experiences, was not selected.

Mwita (2022) posited five factors that affect data saturation in qualitative research design: pre-determined codes and themes, sample size, relevancy of research subjects (respondents), number of research methods, and length of data collection session. Data saturation in the case study was achieved primarily through the sample size, pre-determined themes, relevant research participants, and a singular research method. Data saturation in qualitative research is achieved when the researcher has reached a full understanding of the participants' perspectives (Saunders et al., 2018). When there is no new information, coding, or themes inherent in the research, and the research results can be replicated, data saturation will be achieved (Fusch & Ness, 2015). I reviewed data information, coding, and themes; when there was no new information, and the research results can be replicated, I reached data saturation in the study.

Population and Sampling

The sampling method for this case study was purposeful. Researchers utilize purposeful sampling techniques in qualitative research for the selection and identification

of cases with rich information and context (Jameson, 2017). The purposeful sampling method was used to identify and select the most relevant and information-rich participants for this case study. The sample size for qualitative studies is typically small and purposeful sampling is the most effective sampling method when resources are limited (Pournajaf et al., 2023). The participants for this case study were two mid-level managers and two senior executives from a Head Start program located in the Northern Region of the United States with multiple service locations. The use of purposive sampling to recruit participants helped to identify subject-matter experts who had prior expertise and experience with the phenomenon, as recommended by Bergman et al. (2024).

To increase the validity of the qualitative case study results, multiple factors were utilized to ensure data saturation. Data saturation in qualitative research is achieved when the researcher has reached a full understanding of the participants' perspectives (Saunders et al., 2018). When there is no new information, coding, or themes inherent in the research, and the research results can be replicated, data saturation will be achieved (Fusch & Ness, 2015). Three of the five factors touted by Mwita (2022) that affect data saturation are pre-determined themes, sample size, and the relevancy of the research participants. Pre-determined themes from the literature review were used as a guide to categorize research responses. The selected research participants were required to have lived experiences that are relevant to the exploration of the phenomena.

Participation criteria are established by researchers to ensure that participant possess experience and knowledge related to the phenomenon under study (Gallegos et

al., 2023). Participants were recruited based on both their experience and accessibility. The sample size was small, which consisted of four participants. I did not have to recruit additional participants because I reached data saturation with four participants. Participants selected in the study participated in a voluntary interview. To be eligible for participation in the study, the participant (a) must have been a past or present full-time employee for at least 2 years in a mid-level manager or senior executive role and (b) must have participated in the implementation of communication strategies to increase communications between program and financial operations to increase profitability.

According to Harvey et al. (2024), in case studies where the potential population may be hard-to-reach, selecting an audio interview setting provides a high level of confidentiality for participants, choice of location, convenience, and reduced time commitments from researchers and participants. The interview setting selected for this case study was my office. I used Zoom, Microsoft Teams, or the telephone to conduct the semistructured interviews. My office was a quiet, private space with doors, which were locked to limit interruption and protect participants' confidentiality. Potential participants could have been reluctant to participate in this case study if I would not have been unable to implement strategies to protect their confidentiality. Using my office as the interview environment was appropriate for the study because protecting the confidentiality of the participants was an ethical requirement for this case study.

Ethical Research

The process of communication between the researcher and potential research participants is described as informed consent (Eeckhout et al., 2023). Informed consent

safeguards data protection and privacy rights. Effective informed consent processes ensure that research participants are given information regarding research participation, allow participants to make autonomous decisions about whether they want to participate, and affirm that participants understand the research participation information prior to conducting the study (Eeckhout et al., 2023). Obtaining informed consent from participants in this case study before conducting research was both a Walden University and an ethical research requirement. Participants were emailed the informed consent form the day before the interview.

The purpose of the informed consent process was to obtain a reasonable assurance that research participants understood the study and their contribution to the study. A valid informed consent process is a complex process interwoven with many economic and sociocultural factors including the exchange of adequate information with research participants, clearly defining the participants' voluntariness, and ensuring the participant has a clear comprehension of the process (Nguyen et al., 2023). Socioeconomic and demographic characteristics, such as age, economic status, and low education present barriers to the informed consent process, which must be addressed to improve participant understanding and enhance the quality of the informed consent process (Nguyen et al., 2023). Research participants are conveyed study-related information and provided with access to informed consent documentation before and after signing the consent (De Sutter et al., 2023). Participants electronically provided consent to participate in the study by replying "I consent" to the invitation email. Email documentation of consent to participate was collected and verified 15 minutes before the participant interview.

Researchers used both verbal and written communication strategies to inform participants of their liberty to withdraw from the project, skip interview questions, move interview questions to the end of the interview, and provided an opportunity for the participants to ask questions (Tomas & Bidet, 2024). Participants could have withdrawn from the study at any time before, during, or after data collection without penalty, retaliation, or mistreatment. Participants could have withdrawn from participating in the study by requesting the researcher either verbally, electronically through e-mail, or by telephone. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw verbally on the day of interview or via written communication. According to Yin (2018), offering incentives and enticements could potentially yield biases in participant responses, thereby damaging the integrity of the study. Incentives are strictly prohibited by Walden University's IRB. Participation in the study was strictly voluntary, and no incentives were given to participants.

Business leader emailed consent documentation will be stored securely in an electronic file for 5 years and then destroyed. Researchers used redaction and blurring techniques to protect participant demographics and identify information (Campbell et al., 2023). To protect the privacy of the research participants and ensure confidentiality, all identifying information was redacted from interview transcripts, organizational documents, and data collected. Data collected will be maintained in a safe place for 5 years to protect the rights of participants. The IRB approval number for this study is 02-07-25-1010891.

Data Collection Instruments

According to Richards et al. (2023), the qualitative researcher is the primary data collection instrument. I was the primary data collection instrument. Researchers used semistructured interviews as an effective data collection instrument to gain insight into the hidden aspects of a phenomenon that are not immediately perceptible (Belina, 2023). Karunaratna et al. (2024) touted that reviewing organizational documents is generally easier and less expensive to obtain; however, researchers using this secondary data collection source must carefully evaluate the documents validity, accuracy, and relevance before using in their case study. The data collection process included dissemination of the research interview questions, one-on-one semistructured interviews with each participant, and the review of organizational documents. Research questions were forwarded to participants 2-5 business days prior to the scheduled interview. The interview questions are in Appendix A.

Anecdotal notes for individual participant responses during the semistructured interview were recorded on the interview questions instrument. Interviews were audio recorded, and transcripts were created using software in Microsoft Teams. According to Anis and Tan (2024), recording interviewee transcripts and conducting subsequent transcription reviews is essential to assure the reliability and validity of the qualitative data. Member checking was implemented to enhance the reliability and validity of the data collection process. Member checking is a participant validation process that enhances the rigor of qualitative research wherein participants review and verify the researchers' written interpretation of participants' responses (Sahakyan, 2023).

I conducted the interview, and I transcribed each participant's recording of the interview. Participants were provided with a copy of my written interpretation of their responses to the interview questions to verify and validate the accuracy of my interpretations. Recommended changes or corrections were recorded on the written interpretation of the transcript and returned electronically. Alternatively, participants could communicate changes via a phone conversation.

Data Collection Technique

Semistructured interviews are widely used in many types of qualitative and quantitative research studies (Saliya, 2023). The interview protocol sample describing what was done and what was said are located in Appendix B. Verbal permission to record the interview was obtained from each participant prior to conducting the interview via video conference or telephone. Questions were asked one by one allowing the participant to respond to each question. The open-ended interview questions in the semistructured interview process allows for rigorous, systemic, and structural coverage of key topics while allowing for a degree of freedom and adaptability in seeking information from the interviewees and for new ideas and themes to emerge (Schnitzler et al., 2023).

I recorded hand-written anecdotal notes during the interview process on the data collection instrument for each participant. Clarifying questions were asked of participants only if responses were not clear. Immediately after each interview by video, I requested and reviewed the audio transcript from the video conference software. For interviews conducted by telephone, a digital recording device could have been used to audio record the interview and phone audio recordings could have been reviewed to ensure the

accuracy of my written notes transcribed during the interview process. Participant approval of data accuracy through review of researcher written interpretation of their responses is a key instrument of ensuring data quality in qualitative research (Sahakyan, 2023). My interpretation of the transcripts were sent to participants for review and validation. My interpretation of the transcripts were utilized to create a research log of detailed responses to each participant's interview questions via a spreadsheet.

Advantages to using the semistructured interview data collection technique include achieving high compatibility with various forms of data analysis, allowing for assessment and analysis of data in a variety of ways, using dual tools for gathering data in both quantitative and qualitative studies, and specifying general questions to clarify and explore research phenomena (Mansoor et al., 2023). Disadvantages of using the semistructured interview data collection technique include language barriers, limited understanding of the topical subject, potential data losses, poor active listening skills, and third-party approvals or permissions to conduct the interviews (Kakilla, 2021).

Advantages of reviewing organizational documents as a data collection technique include providing a context for understanding background or historical information, less expensive to obtain, easier to access, provides a foundation for designing the study, and can be used as a tool to compare results (Karunarathna et al., 2024). Disadvantages of reviewing organizational documents as a data collection technique include reliability concerns, may not be suitable to the specific needs of current research, and researchers bear the responsibility to evaluate the validity, accuracy, and relevance of the data before using them in their studies (Karunarathna et al., 2024).

Data Organization Technique

Implementing an administrative technique for the process of data management ensures the reliability of the data and is helpful for storing, validating, and processing indispensable data (Sharma et al., 2023). A spreadsheet was used to keep track of participant responses. Case study participants were given a numerical identifier based on the order they were interviewed. For example, case study participant 1 (PAR-1), case study participant 2 (PAR-2), case study participant 3 (PAR-3), and case study participant 4 (PAR-4). Responses were cataloged based on pre-determined themes. Emerging themes were documented and cataloged. Walden University's IRB requirements include an ethical obligation that researchers keep raw data, which includes recordings, for 5 years and then permanently destroy all forms of the raw data (Walden University, 2024). All raw data, recorded interviews, interview questions, written responses, transcripts, logs, and tracking spreadsheets were stored securely and will be maintained for a period of 5 years.

To support the trustworthiness of the qualitative analysis, data must be organized, systemic, and iterative (Bingham, 2023). Data organization was an essential factor in ensuring the security and viability of data. Effective organization of data that has been collected from different authentic sources for the present research assists with the employment of systematic and thematic analysis (Sharma et al., 2023). Themes were identified after the conclusion of all participant interviews. Researchers utilized deductive and inductive coding strategies to effectively organize data (Bingham, 2023). A color categorization process was used to systematically analyze and organize data via themes.

When the main data source in a qualitative study is interview transcripts or field notes, a reconciliation process is critical to enhancing the transparency and consistency of research data analysis quality and reliability (Cole, 2023).

Data Analysis

The data analysis process for qualitative studies included reducing, simplifying the data by summarizing, paraphrasing, and transcribing field notes, organizing the data to display the findings (Fischer & Biemann, 2024). The type of data analysis that was used in this case study to analyze the data was methodological triangulation. Specifically, I explored the consistency of data obtained by comparing data obtained from internal documentation to data obtained from interviews of the participants to the literature review. There are four types of triangulations identified by Denzin in the 1970s included: (1) data triangulation; (2) investigator triangulation; (3) theory triangulation; and (4) methodological or method triangulation (Hales et al., 2010). Triangulation in research means using multiple datasets, methods, theories, and/or investigators to address a research question. Methodological triangulation involves multiple uses of data sources, in comparison to corroborate facts or phenomenon (Yin, 2018). Methodological triangulation was appropriate for the qualitative case study research design that I used in the study because corroboration of the data collected using multiple sources assisted me in determining construct validity. Methodological triangulation as a research strategy assists researchers with enhancing the validity and credibility of the case study findings (Permatasari et al., 2023).

The interview data and organizational documents collected during this study were organized and coded by theme. Researchers use Microsoft (MS) Excel to create themes, seamlessly review and code excerpts of data to analyze, log large volumes of raw data, complete thematic analysis, organize data, and track changes and trends (Grummert & Haslerig, 2024). MS Excel was used to complete coding, and to record, identify, and track themes during the data analysis process. Initial themes identified during the literature review were added to a MS Excel spreadsheet in Column A and color coded. A separate tab in MS Excel was used to track and identify new themes from interview data and organizational documents.

Microsoft Teams or Zoom technology was used to transcribe the audio recordings from participant interviews into detailed transcripts. The use of technology in qualitative and mixed method enhances the quality of the data analysis process by improving competency, reducing human error factors, presenting opportunities for data integration, and the ease of usage for organizing substantial amounts of data (Salmona et al., 2022). Prior to coding the data collected, my interpretation of the transcripts were sent to participants for review and validation.

Content analysis is commonly used for analyzing qualitative data and allows the researcher to evaluate theoretical issues to heighten an understanding of the data collected (Mattimoe et al., 2021). The content analysis process is as follows: (a) identify units of analysis (b) develop coding categories, (c) create and apply coding rules to data, (d) analyze the coded data, and (e) draw conclusions based on findings (Pierre, 2025). I used content analysis to identify emerging themes for coding. After a theme was identified, I

added it to MS Excel, color coded it and added the interview notes or organizational document content used to support my decision. Emerging themes and initial themes were then compared for opportunities to reduce and summarize data themes. A single summary sheet was created in MS Excel to analyze and prepare the results to be used for articulating the case study findings.

Before a researcher publishes or presents the findings for a study, they should search for new articles published since the writing of the proposal and include any relevant findings (Johnson & Christensen, 2024). I searched for new studies published since the writing of the proposal and included them in the presentation of findings. I focused on key themes identified during the study and updates to the conceptual framework. I correlated my findings with the conceptual framework. Relevant findings were included and presented in this case study.

Reliability and Validity

To contribute to the reliability and validity of this case study, I maintained both a researcher's journal and an electronic master journal to analyze the data collected. I conducted a member checking process by sharing my interpretation of participants' responses with each research participant which provided them with an opportunity to validate the integrity of the data collected. Member checking, conducted by presenting researchers' written interpretation of the transcripts for participants to verify and review, is a relatively straightforward process that adds credibility to the data (McKim, 2023).

According to Rose and Johnson (2020), researchers consider credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability to increase trustworthiness when

determining the validity and reliability of qualitative research. Assessing the validity and reliability of study findings requires researchers to make judgments about the accuracy of the research in relation to the application and appropriateness of the methods used and the integrity of the final conclusions (Coleman, 2022). Reliability and validity are not synonymous in qualitative research. For the purpose of this study, the definitions and applicability of reliability and validity techniques are further outlined.

Reliability

According to Declercq and van Poppel (2023), researchers can increase reliability by taking additional measures that include extensive documentation, an iteration pattern of literature-data-literature-data, and transparent reporting with contextualized results. Reliability in qualitative research also refers to the consistency of the analysis and whether the results can be repeated is known as dependability (Rose & Johnson, 2020). I ensured dependability by documenting the interview process and procedures properly and consistently during the data collection process to increase the probability that the results and findings are repeatable by other researchers.

My written interpretations were sent to participants for review and validation. Member checking eliminates the possibility of misrepresentation during the data analysis process (McKim, 2023). Researcher written interpretations of participants' responses were provided to participants to verify the accuracy of the data collected. Participant feedback was used to ensure the accuracy of the data. Additionally, rigorous review to mitigate errors and ensure careless mistakes are not present in the study's conceptual framework, the data collection process, interpretation of the findings, or report of the

results add to the reliability of a research study (Rose & Johnson, 2020). I conducted a rigorous review to eliminate errors and ensure mistakes are not present in the reporting of results, data collection process, interpretation of findings or the study's conceptual framework.

Validity

Transparent presentation of research results is the primary concern of validity in qualitative research (Declercq & van Poppel, 2023). Researchers must determine if the research design was valid for the methodology and if the results were valid based on the sample and context. The lack of attention to ensure or increase validity measures is a common threat and reason for the rejection of a qualitative research proposal (Coleman, 2022). The credibility or correctness of the results, descriptions, conclusions, interpretations, explanations, and overall account of the qualitative research refers to the validity of the study (Coleman, 2022). Data were collected from research participant interviews and organizational documents to obtain a holistic view of the business phenomenon and appropriately evaluate the findings. I utilized methodological triangulation to analyze and synthesize the data obtained from interviews and organizational documents. Methodological triangulation was used to ensure the validity of the research study. Rose and Johnson (2020) claimed that methodological triangulation was a way of exploring various levels and perspectives of the data.

I achieved credibility by adhering to the protocols and process of (a) pattern matching, (b) methodological triangulation of data sources, and (c) member checking in the study. Transferability and credibility referred to the results of a study that aligned

with other contexts, which was an objective of the study, given its case study design with purposeful sampling (Rose & Johnson, 2020). When the findings from a research study can be extrapolated and applied to alternative contexts or situations this is known as transferability (Ahmed, 2024). I achieved transferability in the study when the strategies presented could be applied to alternative business situations or context.

Confirmability refers to the extent to which the study results are supported by the data (Yin, 2018). A rigorous review process was completed to address the confirmability of the research study. Data were documented via audio recording, member checked with written notes and written journal, then logged, organized, and tracked via MS Excel to enhance the confirmability of this study. Researchers linked dependability and confirmability together as trustworthiness criteria heavily dependent upon an external audit or peer-review process (Malmqvist et al., 2024). Walden University's DBA case study requirement was used as an audit process for this research case study. This research study will be reviewed by a DBA Program's appointed committee. Data saturation was achieved once responses were received from four of the participants, there were no new information inherent in the research, and the research results could be duplicated. Data saturation in qualitative research is achieved when the researcher has reached a full understanding of the participants' perspectives (Saunders et al., 2018). When there is no new information, coding, or themes inherent in the research, and the research results can be replicated, data saturation will be achieved (Fusch & Ness, 2015).

Transition and Summary

Section 2 included the purpose of the case study, the role of the researcher, participant descriptors, the research methodology and design, population and sampling, ethical research and informed consent process, data collection, data organization techniques, data analysis, and reliability and validity. I conducted semistructured interviews with two mid-level managers and two senior executives from a Head Start program located in the Northern Region of the United States to explore strategies used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Data saturation was achieved once responses were received from the four participants, there was no new information inherent in the research, and the research results could be duplicated. Once the data were collected, I shared my written interpretations with the research participants to conduct member-checking and ensured the validity of the data. In Section 3, a brief summary of the case study findings is presented. The presentation of findings include overarching themes, application to professional practice, implications for social change, recommendations for action and further research, reflections, and the study's conclusion.

Section 3: Application to Professional Practice and Implications for Change

Introduction

In this section, the findings of the study, a discussion of emergent themes, application to professional practice, implications for social change, recommendations for action and further research, reflections, and my conclusions are presented. The purpose of this qualitative single case study was to explore strategies used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Research was conducted to gain an understanding of the phenomena through the voices of the participants from their lived experiences, insight, and perspectives. To answer the research question, I collected data via semistructured interviews with two mid-level managers and two senior executives from one Head Start program in the Northern Region of the United States. Organizational documents were provided and reviewed to support the strategies touted during the semistructured interviews. Strategies were explored through the lens of the BPR contextual framework, which focused on identifying, analyzing, and improving organizations' key business processes to map the as-is, analyze the as-is, and model the to-be processes. Based on participants' responses and organizational document reviews, five themes emerged related to strategies used to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability: (a) leadership role, (b) organizational culture change, (c) meeting frequency and inclusive attendance, (d) access to data, and (e) training.

Presentation of the Findings

The central research question was: What strategies do Head Start Program leaders use to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability? Five themes emerged from the data analysis process: (a) leadership role, (b) organizational culture change, (c) meeting frequency and inclusive attendance, (d) access to data, and (e) training. Semistructured interview data and organizational documents were collected from two mid-level managers and two senior executives from one Head Start program in the Northern Region of the United States. The participants' semistructured interview responses were recorded via audio recording and handwritten notes. Audio responses and handwritten notes were then used to create a written document of my interpretation of participants' responses. The entire written document of my interpretation was emailed to each participant for validation via a member-checking process. Participants were allowed to correct, clarify, validate, add additional information, and confirm that my interpretation accurately reflected their responses.

After conducting member checking, responses to each question were analyzed for content. As themes emerged during content analysis, themes were documented via Microsoft Excel. The themes were color-coded and then assigned to each participant's responses. If a response was applicable to multiple themes, a point was assigned for each theme. Organizational documents were provided by an administrative assistant who did not participate in the study. Due to file size, organizational documents were collected via email or provided for review via the mailing of a data flash drive. Samples of 29 organizational document files were collected, redacted, analyzed, and stored

electronically in the research data electronic filing system. Organizational documents were analyzed before the document was assigned to emergent themes. The types of organizational documents collected and analyzed will be discussed in detail within each theme. A point was assigned for each theme if a response was applicable to multiple themes.

The frequency of the number of responses per identified theme and the percentage of frequency of responses is shown in Table 1. Most of the responses were attributed to organizational culture change, with 89 responses from participants and organizational document reviews. The second highest number of responses was related to the communication channel type, meeting frequency, and inclusive attendance at 44 responses. Training of program managers and access to financial data were the third and fourth highest themes identified at 41 and 32 responses, respectively. The lowest number of responses were attributed to the leadership role at 24 responses. Figure 1 displays the percentage of frequency of responses per identified theme. An additional literature review search was conducted for each emergent theme for articles posted since the approved proposal. Findings for each theme and additional literature are further discussed within each theme subsection.

Table 1

Frequency of Responses per Identified Theme

Identified Themes	<i>n</i>	% of frequency of responses
Meeting Frequency & Inclusive Attendance	44	19%
Organizational Culture Change	89	39%
Access to Data	33	14%

Training	41	18%
Leadership Role	24	10%

Note: n = frequency

Figure 1

Percent of Frequency of Responses per Identified Theme

Theme 1: Leadership Role

Head Start program leaders played an essential role in successfully executing strategies to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Leadership introduction of the strategies and participation in the implementation process were two effective strategies touted by all four participants in this study. According to PAR-2, the management improvement plan (MIP), goals, and action steps were shared initially with the team via an email from the Head Start leader in charge of the project. The goal was to improve the fiscal data's visibility so that available funds could be used to improve program quality and innovation.

The problem to be resolved by these strategies was that resources were not fully maximized to innovate programs and/or improve program quality. The Head Start leader indicated that, on average, it was estimated that \$150,000 to \$200,000 were available to reprogram annually. The Head Start leader explained that early identification of additional resources could be used for program innovation and quality initiatives; therefore, it was necessary to increase program managers' access to fiscal data and their capacity to use fiscal data in the decision-making process. Critical issues to be addressed included management access to fiscal data and management utilization of fiscal data in the decision-making process. The MIP measurable process objective was that 90% of all program managers would be trained and have access to real-time fiscal data to make informed decisions by the specified date. The MIP measurable outcome objective was that 85% of surplus funding be identified early and reprogrammed for innovative projects and quality improvements by the specified date.

It was the involvement of leadership that resulted in the outline of the vision, communicate the vision effectively, and delegate responsibilities for executing the strategy to the team. According to PAR-2, "having senior leadership introduce the MIP set the tone at the top that communication between departments was important." PAR-2 stated that the Head Start leader identified the managers who would participate in the MIP and developed a 26-step MIP action plan indicating all the milestones, due dates, and individuals responsible for each step in the process. PAR-2 further indicated that strategic steps in the action plan included developing and scheduling fiscal training specifically designed for program managers, getting program managers access to real-

time fiscal data, scheduling one-on-one meetings to gauge program manager understanding, completing surveys to determine access and additional training needs, developing service area budgets, working collaboratively on grant application processes, and assessing progress periodically. Before the strategic project was launched, senior leadership held an in-person meeting and presented the overall MIP via a PowerPoint presentation to the program and fiscal managers required to participate in the implementation process.

Once the project was launched, PAR-1 stated that “we began to see communication improvements not just between fiscal and program managers but also between senior leadership and fiscal.” PAR-1 indicated that leaders participated in the MIP trainings and surveys. The programmatic and fiscal communications environment was expanded to include senior leadership positions. Senior leaders, along with the fiscal and program managers, began to meet twice a month for progress meetings. PAR-1 stated that “lateral communication strategies helped me to improve the effectiveness of my communications with organizational leadership.”

Mid-level managers recognized and gained an appreciation of the importance of having senior leadership support and agreement up front when initiating organization-wide strategies. PAR-3 claimed that failing to obtain agreement and support upfront would have made the implementation and onboarding of the strategies difficult. Laying a collaborative foundation with leadership buy-in up front is critical to the successful implementation of strategies that affect the entire organization according to all four participants. As a systems designer and mid-level manager, PAR-1 touted that “I would

have started with a brainstorming session that included all key leaders, program managers, and fiscal operations managers.” The purpose of the brainstorming session would be to share the intent of increasing profitability, increasing operational efficiencies, sharing suggestions, providing an opportunity to collaborate and integrate suggestions, and expanding communications for concerns and questions up front rather than trying to implement without decision-maker buy-in up front. In this study, I found that failing to obtain senior leadership buy-in with specific aspects of strategy implementation led to delays in final approvals, additional discussions and follow-up meetings, challenging decisions made, and neglecting the assignment of important tasks. Obtaining senior leadership buy-in mitigated some of these “negative kickbacks,” according to PAR-3.

Organizational documents collected and reviewed that supported the findings of this theme included: (a) email correspondence, (b) meeting minutes and agenda, (c) training sign-in sheets, (d) MIP goals, (e) 26-step MIP action plan, and (f) Office of Head Start Management Systems Wheel. In this study, I found that Head Start leaders used an email to initiate the launch of the MIP and establish the yearly goals, communicate progress throughout the training phases, and report outcomes. Leadership engagement was further supported by the meeting minutes, agendas, and training sign-in sheets, which documented their communication with management staff and participation in the strategic plan implementation. I reviewed an email correspondence where leadership reported the outcomes of year 1 implementation, encouraged management to continue MIP progress, and officially launched year 2 of the MIP. Organizational documents were

consistent with participant responses regarding the Head Start leader's involvement in the communication strategy implementation process. A total of 29 organizational documents were collected and reviewed. There were seven organizational documents, which accounted for 29% of the 24 frequency responses related to the leadership involvement theme (see Table 2).

Table 2

Leadership Role Theme Frequency of Responses

Leadership Role Theme	<i>n</i>	% of frequency of responses
PAR-1	5	21%
PAR-2	1	4%
PAR-3	4	17%
PAR-4	0	0%
Buy-In	4	17%
Leadership Role in Management Improvement Plan & Process	3	13%
Organizational Documents	7	29%

Note: n = frequency

Conceptual Framework

Leadership role findings in this study tie to the conceptual framework and are consistent with literature review findings. All four participants linked the leadership role and access to data through information technology as catalysts for improving organizational performance to increase communication and profitability. BPR was used as a predictor of organizational performance and the shared relationship between top management commitment, leadership change, and the adoption and use of information technology, as recommended by Genty et al. (2025). All four participants highlighted the shared relationship between the leadership role to influence the attitudes and behaviors of

managers' adoption of communication strategies and the successful implementation of communication strategies to mitigate silos. Head Start leaders in this study shifted from a top-down autocratic approach to a flat company structure, re-engineering radically redesigned business processes to achieve improvements in quality, communications, service, profits, and operational efficiencies, which supports the work of Warren and Ford (2025).

Existing Literature

The findings from this study confirm current literature, which highlighted the importance of the involvement of leadership in organizational strategy implementation. Organizational leadership played a critical role in the development and facilitation of strategies that enhance organizational performance, which supports the work of Ijaz et al. (2025). In this study, I found that top management support or leadership involvement had a significant impact on the adoption of innovation, use of organization resources, design of performance evaluation systems, change of management, and implementation of strategies, which supports the work of Ou and Zhang (2025). Furthermore, there was a positive relationship that existed between the influence of the organization leader and successful organizational outcomes, performance, and strategic direction, which supports the work of other researchers (Ijaz et al., 2025).

All four participants explained that leadership participation in the development, introduction, communication, and support of strategies to increase communication and profitability were critical to successful implementation. The strategic direction and overall performance of an organization was shaped by the characteristics, values, and

experiences of the organization's leader (Ijaz et al., 2025). Ou and Zhang (2025) stressed the importance of the leader's role in repeatedly communicating and stressing the importance of strategic initiatives, actively developing strategic plans, and participation in the implementation process. Leadership styles that encouraged teamwork, commitment, and working toward the same goals included transformational, democratic, laissez-faire, and transactional (Mfuni, 2025). In this study, I found that effective leadership was a key driver in initiating successful communication strategies, selecting or designing successful communication strategies, and implementing new strategies that resulted in sustained organization-wide changes.

Theme 2: Organizational Culture Change

In this study, I found that implementing positive organizational culture change was an effective strategy used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. All four participants echoed sentiments regarding employee empowerment and engagement, collaborative grant writing, budgeting and management processes, data sharing via safe spaces, inclusive budget processes, service area budgets, and the early identification of profits as the benefits gained from changing the organizational culture so that it was more conducive to increased communication. Before implementing these strategies to increase communication, the organizational culture was described by PAR-1 as “tense, uncomfortable, and trepidatious.” The post-implementation organizational culture was described as open, cooperative, collaborative, and congenial. PAR-4 stated that “everyone works together to achieve the end goal of serving the community, children,

and families.” Budgets and grant applications that were previously prepared only by fiscal managers and a director were now a collaborative project between program and fiscal managers according to all four participants. According to all four participants, program managers had service area budgets that are actively managed and reviewed at least monthly for reprogramming.

According to PAR-2, “profits from employee turnover or underspending in program areas were calculated at mid-year and managers and fiscal staff worked together to successfully reprogram funds into a new spending plan.” Additionally PAR-2 indicated that both fiscal and program staff assisted with the early identification of budget surplus proactively throughout the grant year. Through organizational document review, I found that new spending plans included reinvestments to quality improvement, improvements to learning environments, or assessments of health and safety related concerns. PAR-4 indicated that early identification of surplus was used to provide staff retention bonuses, hearing screening equipment, complete mental health initiatives, complete education curriculum initiatives, parent at home activity software and services, dental initiatives, lead initiatives, healthy drinking water initiatives, baby formula initiatives, and other projects to support the provision of high-quality comprehensive services.

All four participants indicated that prior to implementing these strategies to increase communication, they were not identifying surplus funds early enough in the program year to reinvest in the program. PAR-3 indicated that funds were left on the table that could have been used to improve the quality of the comprehensive services provided to the children, families, and communities being served. Managers learned

through this process that they “accomplished more by sharing data and working together” according to PAR-2. Although no formal assessment of the organizational culture was taken, PAR-1 stated that they “observed the improvements” to operational efficiencies, employee morale, managers' confidence and comfort levels, and business processes over time.

In this study, I found that to increase accountability and add additional fiscal oversight, individual program managers were trained and given the responsibility of being involved in drafting their own departmental budgets, tracking their expenses, creating cost allocation plans, being cognizant of regulations for purchasing, obtaining quotes, entering purchase orders, and handling invoices, among others. According to PAR-2 and PAR-4, fiscal processes were changed to include program managers upfront, wherein fiscal would complete the final review and approval to ensure compliance and allowability. The process changes added more accountability and oversight according to PAR-2. In this study, I found that program managers were empowered, and their level of comfortability increased with the responsibility of managing budgets and making purchasing decisions without constant oversight. According to PAR-3, adjustments such as adding additional credit cards for program purchases related to food, health, and professional development helped with the “acceptance of and ease of the new process.” Additionally PAR-2 indicated that an unintended outcome of implementing this type of business strategy to improve communications was the boost to employee morale. According to all four participants, program managers expressed feeling valued and trusted with greater responsibility. Fiscal managers expressed feeling relief about sharing

some of the accountability and compliance load with program managers according to PAR-2. PAR-4 stated that “compliance is not just a fiscal responsibility; this responsibility belongs to everyone in the program.”

In this study, I found that employee engagement and buy-in were critical to the success of implementing strategies to increase communication and profitability. According to PAR-3, employee engagement ensured that managers understood what they were being asked to do and “why the change was important.” Additionally PAR-3 indicated that the organization had many valued employees who had been with the agency for a very long time, and change was difficult. However, when employees understood the why, they bought in with renewed determination to help the organization achieve the end goal despite the difficulty according to PAR-3. With renewed determination, the organization “continued with the end goal in mind” (PAR-3) despite any setbacks or roadblocks encountered. PAR-3 indicated that they did not give up because of difficulty or negative feedback; instead, they adjusted the plan, continually stayed on top of process changes, and advocated for movement to ensure goals were achieved.

In this study, I found that an organizational culture that focused on employee engagement and team building created an environment for continuous process improvements. PAR-3 stated that “if you don't have a strong team or you're not continually working to have a strong team, whatever you're working on is not going to improve.” Both program managers and fiscal managers have a heart for the work that the overall organization was doing for the community, children, families, and staff according

to all four participants. Additionally, according to all four participants, when both sets of managers kept the big picture in mind, it was easier to obtain the buy-in necessary to implement better communication strategies successfully.

Organizational documents collected and reviewed that supported the findings of this theme included: (a) Office of Head Start Management System Wheel, (b) service area budgets, (c) grant application process document, (d) meeting agenda and minutes, (e) surplus spending plans, (f) training cheat sheets, (g) service area budgets, (h) financial statements, (i) pivot table YTD expenses report, (j) MIP 26 action steps, (k) MIP introduction email, and (l) fiscal one-on-one follow-up checklist. All documents reviewed supported the organizational culture changes from an environment of silos to one that was more team oriented, collaborative, supportive, and integrated with program and fiscal efficiencies. The Office of Head Start Management Systems Wheel illustrated in Figure 2 documented the typical components of the management systems in Head Start programs. Through organizational document review, I found that there are 12 management systems in the Head Start management wheel. Additionally, I found that all service areas have an equal portion of the management systems wheel, indicating the collaboration required between all service areas to achieve the common goals and objectives of the Head Start program.

Program governance provided by the organization's board of directors in collaboration with the parents of Head Start children lay the foundation for accountability, transparency, fiduciary responsibility, and parent engagement in their children's success (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration for

Children and Families, 2025b). Through observation of Figure 2, I found that governance and leadership are the foundation of effective management and are responsible for informing and encompassing the 12 management systems. The 12 management systems include: Data & Evaluation, Program Planning & Service System Design, Fiscal Management, Community & Self-Assessment, Facilities & Learning Environments, Transportation, Technology & Information Systems, Training & Professional Development, Communication, Recordkeeping & Reporting, Ongoing Monitoring & Continuous Improvement, and Human Resources (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration for Children and Families, 2025b). The governing body/Tribal Council, Policy Council, and management staff comprised the three key entities of leadership of Head Start programs. According to PAR-1, legal and fiscal responsibility for the program is assumed by the governing body/Tribal Council. The Policy Council, comprised from parents of Head Start children, and community members are responsible for setting direction (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration for Children and Families, 2025b). PAR-1 indicated that management staff provide oversight for day-to-day operations. In this study, I found that the governing body, the Policy Council, and the management staff are a powerful combined force providing leadership and strategic direction for the Head Start program.

The yellow circle of Figure 2 outlines the scope of these 12 management systems consistent with the 5-year project period (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration for Children and Families, 2025b). According to PAR-1, the systems support program management, planning, and well-developed oversight systems,

enabling programs to ensure compliance with regulations, increase program quality, and strive for service excellence. The segmented aqua blue ring outlines each of the individual management systems, which work together to inform and influence the program's service delivery, represented in the inner blue circle (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration for Children and Families, 2025b). Service delivery included eligibility determination, recruitment, selection, enrollment, and attendance (ERSEA), education, health, mental health, community partnerships, and family engagement (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration for Children and Families, 2025b). PAR-1 explained that quality child and family outcomes are the intended results when innovative leadership, strong management systems, and well-designed services are working together.

Figure 2

Organizational Leadership: Management Systems Wheel

Note: From <https://headstart.gov/organizational-leadership/article/management-systems-wheel>

A total of 29 organizational documents were collected and reviewed that supported the organizational culture change theme. There were 17 organizational documents that accounted for 19% of the 89 frequency responses related to the organizational culture change theme (See Table 3). Organizational documents reviewed supported participant responses regarding changes to the organizational culture.

Table 3*Organizational Culture Change Theme Frequency of Responses*

Organizational Culture Change Theme	<i>n</i>	% of frequency of responses
PAR-1	10	11%
PAR-2	10	11%
PAR-3	11	12%
PAR-4	10	11%
Empowerment to Make Informed Decision & Comfortability	4	4%
Accountability	4	4%
Buy-in & Employee Engagement	4	4%
Early Identification of Surplus	4	4%
Reprogram Surplus Funds for Innovation & Quality Improvements	4	4%
Collaborative Processes: Grant Writing, Budgeting, & Management	4	4%
Data Sharing - Safe Space	4	4%
Inclusive Budget Process - Service Area Budgets	3	3%
Organizational Documents	17	19%

Note: n = frequency

Conceptual Framework

Organizational culture change findings in this study tie to the conceptual framework and are consistent with literature review findings. All four case study participants indicated that transformational changes in the organizational culture and processes positively enhanced the quality of services provided and impacted people, profitability, and planning. Transformational change was achieved in the key areas of process, people, planning, product, and price through BPR, as recommended by several scholars (Warren & Ford, 2025). In this study, I found that Head Start managers innovated a process that resulted in the early identification of surplus funding, improved processing time, empowered managers, increased communications, added quality to services, and increased efficiency and effectiveness of operations. In this study, I found

that BPR was used to maximize quality, improve performance, enhance utilization of resources, and minimize processing times. The practical implementation of BPR was used to streamline and integrate business processes and achieve breakthroughs in performance, which supports the work of Renna and Colonnese (2025).

Existing Literature

These findings confirm literature review documentation regarding how increased communication strategies positively impact organizational culture. Because resistance to change remains the most significant obstacle to the successful implementation of strategies, organizations must work to fundamentally shift the organizational culture (Kusumawati, 2025). Top-down influences are created that negatively impact the organization's culture when professional silos and team fault lines are maintained (Campos et al., 2025). According to Kusumawati (2025), cross-functional teams bridge the gap between technical and operational expertise, which ensures seamless data integration and utilization. Successful communication must be reflected through human relations and corporate communication activities and must be a part of the organizational culture (Puigvert-Santoro et al., 2025). Violation of an organization norm can be both constructive and destructive (Bennett et al., 2024). In this study, I found that organizational norms that maintain bifurcated silos are destructive to an organization's culture and strategies exist to increase communications and profitability. Furthermore, I found that norms that foster collaboration, teamwork, and inclusiveness are constructive to a positive organizational culture. Kalogiannidis et al. (2025) highlighted the importance of examining the internal communications environment to understand how

the optimization of communication strategies and practices could be used to enhance profitability, resilience, competitiveness, and long-term sustainability. Strategies to bridge silos included collaborative business processes, policy integration, leadership, institutional arrangements, and shared ideas and visions (Buylova et al., 2025).

Mitigating communication silos facilitates an environment for the sharing of ideas and enriches understanding for all (Kronish et al., 2025).

All four participants shared that implementing strategies to increase communication and profitability triggered organizational culture changes. In this study, I found that organization-wide culture changes were heavily dependent upon inclusion, buy-in from both management and senior leadership, and support through the organizations' invisible values and belief systems. Silos created a negative organizational environment that prohibit the sharing of knowledge, skills or information between departments, which supports the work of other researchers (Jones et al., 2024). According to Jones et al. (2024), applying strategies that insisted on a culture of knowledge sharing laid a foundation to foster a culture of collaboration. Hearty collaborations were developed when people of diverse backgrounds, expertise, education, perspectives, traditions, and life experiences come together to provide the ingredients needed for successful project completion (Karajgikar, 2025). Strategies to increase internal communications acted as a catalyst to promote well-being and positively transform organization culture (Puigvert-Santoro et al., 2025).

Theme 3: Meeting Frequency and Inclusive Attendance

In this study, I found that increasing periodic meeting frequency and ensuring inclusive meeting attendance were an effective strategy used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. All four participants indicated that fiscal managers were invited to participate in program managers' meetings to share financial data, budget updates, and regulatory compliance concerns. According to PAR-2, "financial managers actively attend and participate in programmatic meetings." Inclusive attendance at meetings helped the organization to develop a communications environment which PAR-1 described as "one of reciprocity." PAR-3 indicated that having fiscal managers at programmatic meetings saved time and assisted with buy-in. PAR-2 stated that "almost every decision has fiscal implications." Program leaders found that it was much easier to have a fiscal staff person at their program level meetings to hear the needs and work collaboratively with them to resolve issues than to present something that the fiscal operations team would reject due to non-compliance or funding issues according to PAR-3. PAR-4 indicated that when fiscal managers are included, they become a part of the team working to solve the problem from the front end rather than having to reject the solution on the back end.

In this study, I found that increasing meeting frequency provided greater opportunities for collaborations. PAR-2 and PAR-3 indicated that fiscal and program managers established an open-door communication strategy among themselves and began to hold weekly meetings to review and prepare documents for monthly progress and

financial reports. PAR-3 shared that managers worked collaboratively using Microsoft Teams meetings to clarify fiscal and accounting-related matters in real time, which minimized errors in reporting. PAR-1 stated that “setting up standing meetings and creating agendas for the meetings that delineate and review each grant separately” were two critical tools to successfully increasing communication between fiscal and program managers. The investment of time in one-on-one meetings led to learning experiences between program and fiscal operation managers according to PAR-2. PAR-1 explained that program and fiscal managers are content area experts and that the collaboration and sharing of expertise ultimately yielded more informed group meetings and discussions.

PAR-4 touted that in addition to meeting frequency changes, the content of the meeting increased productivity and effectiveness of the team, conflict resolution and problem solving became more diversified, and the overall innovation of the team increased. All four participants shared that managers began to communicate more openly without concerns for the repercussions of disagreeing. An open internal communication work environment allowed for clear communications, clarification, and a better understanding without the constant follow-up questions of "did you mean this or did you mean that" (PAR-1). Additionally, all four participants indicated that the internal communications environment became a safe space to be transparent without fear, which led to an increase in the interjection and diversity of opinions.

In this study, I found that it is important that organizations offer multiple communication channel options to increase overall communications through increased meeting frequency and inclusive attendance. According to PAR-3, “not every employee

will respond equally” to implementing a business strategy; “some respond best to meetings in person or Zoom, others prefer a written procedure to refer to, many prefer a hands-on walk through.” All four participants indicated that, one-on-one check-ins and surveys are necessary to ascertain what methods work best for your team. PAR-3 indicated that assuming one method works for all or that one is better than the other is not productive for implementing business strategy. Periodic budget meetings and occasional one-on-one meetings with program managers revealed that managers were actively looking at their service area budgets due to the questions and or corrections they requested to the financial data according to PAR-2. All four participants indicated that budget negotiations during the grant application process, mid-year review process, and year-end process were an indicator that managers understood their service area needs and were knowledgeable enough to negotiate surplus or articulate overspending and effectively negotiate for what their department could release or demand. According to PAR-4, “truest assessments for profitably came during mid-year review and year-end review processes when surplus funding from employee turnover or underspending was identified and reprogrammed into projects to accomplish program goals that benefit staff, children, families, and the overall community.” In this study, I found that the true financial measurement of the effectiveness of implementing these business strategies to increase meeting frequency and inclusive meeting attendance was evident in the profits identified and successfully reinvested by the team. All four participants agreed that increasing meeting frequency and inclusive meeting attendance were effective strategies used by their organization to mitigate silos and increase profits.

Organizational documents collected and reviewed that supported the findings of this theme included: (a) program meeting minutes, (b) program meeting agendas, (c) fiscal meeting agendas, (d) email correspondence regarding monthly and bi-weekly meetings, (e) financial statements, (f) pivot table reports by department, (g) meeting sign-in sheets, and (h) follow-up one-on-one meeting requests and notes. Meeting minutes, agenda, sign-in sheets, financial statements, and pivot table reports by department supported participant responses regarding meeting frequency increases, fiscal managers inclusion and agenda item at programmatic meetings, and types of reports and data shared during the meetings. One-on-one meeting requests and follow-up notes provided evidence of the increase in meeting frequency between program and fiscal managers. Bi-weekly and monthly meeting correspondence helped to define that periodic meetings for this organization did not mean quarterly, semi-annual, annually, or bi-monthly. There were seven organizational documents which accounted for 16% of the 44 frequency responses related to the meeting frequency and inclusive attendance theme (See Table 4). A total of 29 organizational documents were collected and reviewed.

Table 4

Meeting Frequency and Inclusive Attendance Theme Frequency of Responses

Meeting Frequency and Inclusive Attendance Theme	<i>n</i>	% of frequency of responses
PAR-1	5	11%
PAR-2	8	18%
PAR-3	4	9%
PAR-4	4	9%
Fiscal Invited to Programmatic Meetings	4	9%
1:1 Follow-Up Meeting to Address Specific Concerns	4	9%
Fiscal Has an Agenda Item at Program Meetings	4	9%

Increased Periodic Meetings – Monthly & Bi-Weekly	4	9%
Organizational Documents	7	16%

Note: n = frequency

Conceptual Framework

Meeting frequency and inclusive attendance findings in this study tie to the conceptual framework. BPR is aimed at identifying and correcting existing operational processes that were wasteful and had no inherent benefit (Genty et al., 2025). In this study, I found that Head Start leaders indicated that having meetings without including input from both fiscal and programs managers was a waste of resources. All four participants agreed that increasing meeting frequency and including both program and fiscal managers resulted in quicker financial decisions, innovative solutions to compliance and regulatory challenges, and increased collaborations on projects. According to Renna and Colonnese (2025), BPR provided benefits in terms of efficiency and effectiveness in administrative processes.

Existing Literature

These findings extend knowledge in the discipline of team meetings as an effective communication channel for sharing information across teams and building team synergy within an organization. These findings are consistent with and tied to existing literature on meetings and inclusive attendance as an effective business practice to improve team communication. According to Sari et al. (2025), daily morning briefing meetings improve effective team communication. Through improved information delivery and discussion of services issues, daily briefings improve team communication by 30% (Sari et al., 2025). Organizations can achieve better performance outcomes,

increase employee satisfaction, and reduce employee turnover by integrating inclusive practices (Rahayu et al., 2025). Open communication, effective collaboration, and participatory decision-making are characteristics of a strong culture of inclusion in organizations (Rahayu et al., 2025). Collaborative and creative communication behaviors increase an organization's attractiveness (Puigvert-Santoro et al., 2025). Rahayu et al. (2025) indicated that an inclusive work environment provides the foundation to ensure all voices are heard, enhances productivity and innovation; and supports a culture where employees are respected and valued. The integration of virtual collaboration tools and remote work have become increasingly important in creating inclusive workplaces (Apelehin et al., 2025).

Meeting frequency, inclusive attendance, access to data, and training all fit within the existing academic literature related to the theme of formalized communication channels. Inclusive initiatives are a crucial aspect of organizational transformation and are integral to creating environments where employees feel valued and empowered (Apelehin et al., 2025). Inclusive meeting attendance, increased meeting frequency, access to fiscal data, and training were new channels of formalized business communication strategies discussed by all four participants that they used to successfully increase internal communications, which led to the early identification of surplus funding and profits. Organizations utilize virtual meeting platforms to facilitate communication and collaboration, foster connections and maintain team cohesion, and to organize team building activities and social events (Apelehin et al., 2025). Management used daily morning briefing meetings as a strategy to improve communication, ensure quality

services, and align team goals (Sari et al., 2025). Daily morning meetings were an effective communication tool used to clearly convey information and verify that information was understood (Sari et al., 2025). According to Sari et al. (2025), daily meetings promoted interpersonal communication between staff and helped to emphasize the importance of good communication as an organizational culture expectation.

Theme 4: Access to Data

In this study, I found that providing program managers with access to financial data was an effective strategy used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. According to all four participants, the goal of this strategy was to increase access to financial data so that program managers could make informed decisions based on these data. All four participants explained that program managers did not have access to real-time financial data. Periodic financial statements were provided to managers monthly; however, the financial data were typically historical data according to all four participants. According to PAR-2, PAR-3, and PAR-4, there were several barriers to overcome regarding access to real-time financial data for non-fiscal managers, which included accounting system security protocols, managers' ability to manipulate or change data, and managers' ability to separate their department data from the cumulative financial report data. PAR-4 indicated that accounting system security protocols were resolved by providing program managers with access to two systems that pull reports nightly from the accounting system. PAR-2 explained that a nightly process was completed that loaded financial data into a data warehouse and updated a read-only

financial statement reporting system. Managers could access raw data using Microsoft Excel through the data warehouse or through the financial statement reporting system according to PAR-2. Additionally, PAR-2 indicated that data accessed from both systems was timely and could not be changed, which resolved fiscal staff concerns regarding the manipulation of data. According to PAR-4, fiscal staff were “apprehensive about giving access to financial data to program managers and concerned about the level of follow-up support that would be needed for program managers after training.”

PAR-2 explained that the final barrier to financial data analysis was the separation of the data by the specific departments, which could only be resolved through Microsoft Excel and accounting-specific training provided to managers regarding the general ledger details and chart of accounts. Accounting system transactions could be drilled down to department and location levels using pivot tables in Microsoft Excel, according to PAR-2. PAR-4 indicated that ad hoc reports could be created from the financial reporting system using the same chart of accounts transaction level detail to differentiate service area actual expense data. According to PAR-2, access to the data warehouse and financial statement reporting system required information technology (IT) department review and approval. The organization’s IT manager would not agree to provide access to program managers without verification that they had been trained on how to run reports and how to create pivot tables to review the data from the data warehouse, according to PAR-2. According to PAR-2 and PAR-4, the fiscal manager was responsible for scheduling and conducting program managers' training. PAR-4 explained that after training, the fiscal manager shared the list of program managers who completed the training to the IT

department, and access to both systems was granted. According to PAR-2, implementing this strategy was so successful that “budget management training and financial data read-only access is provided to all managers during the onboarding process.” In this study, I found that MS Excel training was provided and made available to all staff throughout the organization. PAR-2 stated that program managers were “concerned with being responsible for a portion of the budget.” However, all four participants indicated that as strategies were implemented, apprehension turned to excitement for program managers. All four participants echoed that program managers were excited about having their own service area budget, some control over a portion of the agency budget, and their own departmental expenses, and they were excited about opportunities to use identified surplus to innovate or implement new initiatives.

Organizational documents collected and reviewed that supported the findings of this theme included: (a) email confirmation from organization information technology (IT) specialists, (b) MIP survey responses, (c) fiscal staff access follow-up checklist, (d) financial statements, (e) budget comparison reports, (f) service area expense pivot table report, (g) chart of accounts cheat sheets, (h) MS Excel training sign-in sheet, (i) spend down plans for the past four years, and (j) program manager email inquiries and feedback. The email confirmation from IT and MIP Survey responses provided support that program managers had read-only access to the financial data after they completed the training. Pivot table and financial report samples reviewed provided support that program managers can download fiscal data and create a pivot table to review expenses by their department (service area), fiscal data can be downloaded monthly or daily for real-time

fiscal data, each service area manager has their own portion of the overall programs' operational budget, and the accounting system dumps data into the read-only data warehouse nightly. Budget comparison reports supported the idea that program managers receive monthly financial statements with year-to-date expenses for their service area. Training logs and sign-in sheets supported the statements that managers received MS Excel training for data warehouse reporting of fiscal data from the accounting system. A chart of account cheat sheets was reviewed, and it revealed that program managers were provided with cheat sheets to help them understand fiscal data and financial statements. Spend-down plans reflected the total amount of profits identified by program and fiscal managers annually and outlined the reinvestment plans and activities. There were 12 organizational documents collected and reviewed which accounted for 36% of the 33 frequency responses related to the access to data theme (see Table 5). A total of 29 organizational documents were collected and reviewed.

Table 5

Access to Data Theme Frequency of Responses

Access to Data Theme	<i>n</i>	% of frequency of responses
PAR-1	3	9%
PAR-2	8	24%
PAR-3	1	3%
PAR-4	3	9%
Increase Access to Financial Data to Make Informed Decisions	3	9%
Financial Data Security: Barriers for Program Managers	3	9%
Organizational Documents	12	36%

Note: n = frequency

Findings for this theme include that when program managers are given access to real-time financial data, they are empowered to make informed decisions based on financial data and to work collaboratively with fiscal to identify potential profits earlier in the grant cycle. PAR-2 stated that “program staff were now looking at fiscal data, making informed decisions for their service area budget.” All four participants indicated that both fiscal and program managers were working together, which resulted in the early identification of surplus funding, and the earlier the surplus was identified, the earlier it was reprogrammed to improve program quality for staff, children, and the families the program serves. Figure 3 reflects the early identification of profits that were reprogrammed for 4 years while the program was implementing these strategies to increase communications. Program managers and fiscal managers worked collaboratively to identify and reprogram \$308K in year one, \$370K in year two, \$1.2 million in year three, and \$823K in year four.

Figure 3

Profits Identified and Reprogrammed During Strategy Implementation

Note: Funds in US dollars (\$), K = thousands of dollars, mil. = millions of dollars.

Conceptual Framework

The access to data finding in this study ties to the conceptual framework. In this study, I found that an analysis of the existing workflow processes revealed that Head Start program managers' lack of access to data prohibited their ability to make informed financial decisions based on real-time data. BPR included a thorough analysis of existing workflows with the objective of fostering significant process improvements (Renna & Colonnese, 2025). According to PAR-2 and PAR-4, Head Start leaders developed an effective strategy to provide managers with access to read-only, real-time financial data while remaining in compliance with accounting system security challenges and data integrity concerns. BPR was identified as a critical emergent strategy to address challenges with digital transformation, regulatory demands, and organization inefficiencies, which supports the work of Renna and Colonnese (2025). All four participants confirmed that processing times were decreased, program managers gained access to and used existing financial resources, and the quality of the work environment was improved when strategies to increase communication were implemented.

Existing Literature

These findings extend knowledge regarding the importance of sharing access to organizational data so that managers can make informed decisions based on data that is accessible, accurate, and relevant to their body of work. Breaking data silos internally and externally as a strategy optimizes profitability (Chen & Huang, 2025). He et al. (2025) touted that sharing data among diverse members of the organization enabled individuals

to access and collaborate on data in real time, which facilitated faster data-driven decision-making processes and improved the accuracy and efficiency of decisions. Data sharing prevents data silos, increases full data utilization, and enhances data value (He et al., 2025). Adjusting data access rights and data sharing according to business processes improved the overall efficiency of operations (He et al., 2025). Data sharing and access to data promoted collaboration in real time, which facilitated faster data-driven decision-making processes and improved the efficiency and accuracy of decisions (He et al., 2025).

Theme 5: Training

In this study, I found that training was an effective strategy used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. All four participants agreed that training and professional development for program managers on financial data was one of the most effective business strategies for mitigating silos between program and fiscal managers. Program managers were provided with Microsoft Excel training and financial report reading training to analyze financial data according to PAR-2 and PAR-4. PAR-4 shared that the intent of the training was to improve the visibility of fiscal data, increase managers' comfortability with financial reports, and empower managers to be able to make informed decisions about their departmental budgets based on financial data. PAR-3 stated the following:

Spending time training the program managers and lower-level staff on fiscal policies, procedures, and regulations not only save time in processing and

approving, it also provided an overall understanding and appreciation for the entire fiscal process between all levels of staff, from employees to management and vice versa.

Employees understood how and why decisions were made, and fiscal managers were better able to see the needs and responsibilities of employees and managers at the program level according to PAR-2.

In this study, I found that training strategies provided opportunities for fiscal and program managers to communicate. PAR-4 stated, “when fiscal and program managers are working collaboratively together instead of in closed groups, we are able to complete financial processes quicker and more efficiently.” This process also helped program managers' negative opinion of fiscal managers being a "NO person" to change, according to PAR-4. PAR-3 indicated that as program managers were trained in fiscal policies, best practices, regulations, and procedures, they began to understand the compliance pieces, which sometimes required fiscal managers to respond with an answer of “no” to their programmatic request. Instead of accepting the “no”, program managers began to seek fiscal managers' advice on a purchase and found fiscal to be insightful and helpful in supporting them to make allowable purchases according to PAR-2. PAR-4 indicated that financial training was designed and presented by fiscal managers to program managers, which increased their interactions with one another.

PAR-2 indicated that fiscal managers were responsible for supporting program managers' training by being available for one-on-one follow-ups and being responsive to email inquiries regarding financial analysis questions or concerns. PAR-1 stated, “as

managers developed a level of comfort and confidence in their roles, communications became less strained and complaints from the program manager decreased.” PAR-3 stated, “the program managers confidence level grew, and the fiscal manager was impressed with the smart business decisions being made as they became more comfortable.” The fiscal managers regularly checked in with the program managers to ensure they were on the right track and adjusted the process if necessary, according to PAR-2. Program managers were initially apprehensive about learning the financial system, reports, and MS Excel analytical tools; however, at the end of the process, PAR-4 stated that program managers were “grateful for the opportunity to manage their own department budgets.”

PAR-1 indicated that training strategies should be implemented during the onboarding process whenever possible to support the organizational culture of collaborative expectations and deter potential implementation challenges. Because new staff and managers come to the positions with knowledge and experience from previous positions, there was a significant amount of confusion and miscommunication between program and fiscal managers as it related to how things are done differently in Head Start versus the organization's policies and procedures according to PAR-1. PAR-1 further stated that, to mitigate some of this, “I would spend more time during the onboarding process providing specific Head Start regulatory training to both groups of managers.” Successful onboarding processes are critical to integrating employees into the company culture (Bhadane et al., 2025). The goals of a successful onboarding process include providing essential resources and access, ensuring new hires feel welcomed, facilitating

team integration, scheduling training, and aligning the new hire with the company's vision and culture (Bhadane et al., 2025).

Organizational documents collected and reviewed to support the findings of this theme included: (a) grant application training PowerPoint presentation; (b) Head Start 101 training manual; (c) chart of accounts, cost allocation, and financial data cheat sheets; (d) accounting system training certificates; (e) training sign-in sheets; (f) 1:1 follow-up training emails and meeting invites; (g) post-training surveys and results; and (h) program manager email inquiries and feedback. There were nine organizational documents, which accounted for 22% of the 41 frequency responses related to the training theme (see Table 6). A total of 29 organizational documents were collected and reviewed. Training manuals and cheat sheets prepared specifically for program managers documented the fiscal manager's commitment to sharing financial knowledge and data with program managers. Sign-in sheets and certificates from training documented managers' completion of professional development to improve their knowledge and skills with accessing, reading, and interpreting financial data. Training surveys and follow-up emails document the organization's assessment process to measure the effectiveness of the training provided and provide feedback or additional support when needed.

Table 6

Training Theme Frequency of Responses

Training Theme	<i>n</i>	% of frequency of responses
PAR-1	4	10%
PAR-2	8	20%
PAR-3	3	7%

PAR-4	5	12%
Improve Visibility of Fiscal Data	4	10%
Empowerment to Make Informed Decision & Comfortability	4	10%
Financial Training for Program Managers	4	10%
Organizational Documents	9	22%

Note: n = frequency

Conceptual Framework

Training findings in this study tie to the conceptual framework. All four participants shared that investment in the training and professional development of staff to increase communication was a viable tool for increasing workforce capacity and increasing performance. According to Mertens et al. (2024), the seven tenets of BPR were intended as a managerial antidote to cure the negative effects of mediocrity and the traditional corporate structure. The training theme connects to four of the seven principles of BPR, which include having the output users perform the process, incorporating data processing into the process, building decision-making into the process, and capturing data at the source. According to all four participants, program managers were trained to retrieve and read real-time financial data, financial data was incorporated into the business process, managers were empowered to make data-informed decisions, and real-time financial data could be captured directly from the accounting system after training. Head Start leaders' BPR investments in training managers helped them to achieve improvements in staff performance indicators that resulted in increased profits, which supports the work of Warren and Ford (2025). Empowering employees by bridging skills gaps through training and BPR optimizes operational efficiencies which supports the work of Rathnasekara et al. (2025).

Existing Literature

These findings extend knowledge regarding the importance of professional development and training to increase communication between program and fiscal operations to mitigate silos. Training programs, workshops, and working groups provide the meeting space for the communicating and sharing of information, which serves as a bridge to mitigate silos in collaborative business processes (Buylova et al., 2025). To equip employees with the necessary analytical competencies, organizations must invest in workforce training (Kusumawati, 2025). Business strategy implementation is supported by investing in training programs that build capacity by equipping professionals with the necessary skills and expertise needed for successful implementation (Lah, 2025). These findings are consistent with and tied to existing literature on effective business practices related to training as a business strategy. Training increased employee self-confidence and improved employee competency, knowledge, and skills (Rathnasekara et al., 2025). Training, workshops, and work groups provided a meeting ground for networking, socialization, information sharing, and communication of ideas (Buylova et al., 2025).

Applications to Professional Practice

The findings of this study are relevant to improving business practice and could assist business leaders with successful communication strategies to mitigate departmental silos and improve internal communications to increase profitability. The primary objective of this study was to explore strategies used by Head Start Program leaders to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. Leaders can use the five emergent themes: (a) leadership role, (b)

organizational culture change, (c) meeting frequency and inclusive attendance, (d) access to data, and (e) training to develop and implement a successful strategy to increase communications and profits at their organization. These themes may offer potential areas to improve success rates through the application of communication strategies while increasing the potential for increased profits. Insights were provided through each theme regarding transferable business strategies that could be implemented in a broad range of business practices. Organizations can implement these strategies and assess their internal processes for improvements to organization culture, internal communications, and ultimately to yield higher profit margins. In this study, I obtained participants' perspectives on aspects of implementing and assessing successful communication strategies to improve profitability. Data from this research study might add to prior and existing business strategies to improve internal communications within the organization structure. Effective communication strategies support the development of a strong organizational culture, which is crucial to driving organizational transformation (Maddi & Tomasowa, 2025).

This study has applicability to professional practice as business leaders who read this research study may be better informed on successful strategies used to increase communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability. The findings related to the leadership involvement in implementing successful strategies could inspire organizational leaders to support and engage throughout the process of implementation of strategies from start to finish. In this study, I found that as the decision makers, leaders play a key role in managing resources, communicating strategy intent,

using their influence to obtain buy-in, supporting managers with implementation, and determining the amount and type of employee engagement. The success or failure of strategic initiatives rely heavily upon a leader's ability to influence, guide, inspire, and adapt to the needs of the employees and organization (Mfuni, 2025).

Leaders can also practice the strategy that emerged from this study related to meeting frequency, inclusive attendance, and access to data by ensuring that a diverse group of managers are engaged to meet periodically throughout the month to share data regarding their departments. Practicing these strategies improved the organizational culture by increasing opportunities for collaboration and cooperation among managers from different departments. Focusing on communication and team collaboration strategies is key to improving business practices (Samuel et al., 2025). The findings might also help leaders develop training and professional development plans that include financial data to increase and empower managers to make informed decisions using financial data. Training and coaching are applicable to business practice. Participants in this study repeatedly used the word *empowered* to describe how they felt about receiving training and being given access to financial data to make informed decisions regarding their departmental budgets. Business leaders use training initiatives as a strategy for employee empowerment and to enhance employee success (Rathnasekara et al., 2025). Using the findings from this study, business leaders could proactively develop trainings to transform the workforce and encourage behaviors that align with the culture of the organization. The overall successful strategies that emerged from this study resulted in documented profitability consistently for each year of implementation. Leaders may

consider the findings useful for improving overall business operations and increasing their profitability. Organizations that focus on business communication strategies to increase internal communication enhance their sustainability, resilience, and profitability (Kalogiannidis et al., 2025).

Implications for Social Change

When a company makes a concerted effort to operate in a way that enhances, not degrades, society and the environment, they are practicing a corporate social responsibility business model (Yoo et al., 2024). The findings presented in this study could promote positive social change by highlighting successful communication strategies that increase profitability and improve organizational culture. An organizational culture that is collaborative and cooperative results in synergy for a more positive employee workplace experience, thus improving the quality of life for individual employees (Sanusi et al., 2025). Clear, effective, efficient, and streamlined communication contributes to higher employee morale (Nugroho & Wahjoedi, 2024). Celestin et al. (2024) indicated that when business leaders use strategies to enhance employee satisfaction, the benefits include increased profitability and performance and an improved organizational environment. Expanding the understanding of collaborative communication factors and strategies employed by Head Start leaders contributes to positive social change because improving operational efficiencies and investing in the training and professional development of staff improved the social and economic sustainability of the business and its employees.

In the study, I found that successful communication strategy implementation is associated with increased profitability and overall strong financial performance. The increased profits for the organization in this study were reinvested to enhance the overall quality and innovation of the services the organization provides to children, families, staff, and the community. Innovation and quality improvements include opioid crisis initiatives, dental health initiatives, food insecurity support, nutrition education, enhanced mental health services, buses for transportation services, clean-air HVAC system improvements, facility upgrades, playground equipment, staff retention bonuses, and staff wellness activities. Business success fosters a healthy economy, community goodwill, and produces employment (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021). Strong financial performance of the organization contributes to the total economic situation of the private sector, which is essential in creating jobs and reducing unemployment (Faqeerzai et al., 2025). Higher unemployment rates negatively impact the total economic health of the community (Yang, 2025).

Head Start programs provide important services to low-income children and families throughout the United States. Head Start was conceived in 1965 to support children's growth from birth to age five at no cost to income-eligible families through services centered around early learning and development, health, and family well-being (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Administration for Children and Families, 2025a). The services they provide are critical to supporting the war on poverty and to ensuring the health, nutrition, safety, and education of a vulnerable and underserved population. Therefore, it is imperative that Head Start organizations operate

efficiently and effectively so that they can meet the needs of the community, children, and families they serve.

Recommendations for Action

Based on the study's findings, Head Start program leaders and organizational leaders can take the following steps to potentially enhance communication between fiscal and program managers to increase profitability: (a) evaluate the existing communication environment by surveying program and fiscal managers to obtain their opinions, (b) incorporate the communication strategies that emerged from this study into their organizational strategic plan, (c) invest in financial training for program managers, (d) provide read-only access of financial system data to program managers, (e) require inclusive and frequent meetings between fiscal and program managers, and (f) evaluate the implemented communication strategies to determine its usefulness. The leaders who participated in this study shared their knowledge and experience regarding successful strategies to increase communication between fiscal and program managers to increase profitability. I recommend that leaders take action to incorporate the identified communication strategies into their overall strategies for improving communication and increasing profitability. By successfully developing and implementing successful communication strategies, organizations are likely to increase profitability and improve the organizational culture. Internal and external communication are critical to achieving long-term profitability (Hidayat et al., 2024).

The primary target audience for this study is Head Start program leaders and organizational leaders who are interested in increasing their understanding of the factors

influencing successful communication strategy implementation in order to increase communication and profitability. Organizational leaders play an important role in aligning business processes, developing strategies for improvement, and implementing organizational changes (Irwan et al., 2025). Leaders set the tone for accountability and transparency by clearly stating project goals and objectives to employees (Cao et al., 2024). The secondary primary audience is management consultants who work with business leaders to advise them on the development and successful implementation of communication strategies to increase profitability.

Managers may use the findings of this study to develop strategies that focus on building collaborative and cooperative relationships between program and fiscal managers. Collaboration is key to breaking down organizational silos and overcoming communication barriers (Jones et al., 2024). In this study, I found that effective communication methods to be considered include interactive fiscal training for program managers, one-on-one meetings and training, after training surveys, increased meetings, fiscal presence and agenda item at programmatic meetings, periodic sharing of financial data, inclusion and input in the grant application and budget processes up front, and program manager access to real-time financial data. Leaders should ensure that implementations through training are flexible, open, responsive to feedback, and in tune with accomplishing the overall project goals.

Participants noted that mid-level managers were empowered and felt valued being trusted with greater responsibility, access, and accountability of their service area budgets to be able to make informed decisions based on financial data. Therefore, I recommend

that leaders consider the broad benefits to employee morale and their organizational culture that can be obtained through successful communication strategies. In this study, I found that managers should consider forms of communication that are lateral, upward, and downward, which allow feedback through suggestions and give voice to concerns that may help increase organizational profitability. The efficiency and effectiveness of the internal communication channels should be evaluated, and strategies should be developed to address any concerns.

Presentation and publication of this study could be useful. To promote dissemination of the findings to leaders in the Head Start community, I will convey the findings via the following four methods: (a) publishing findings via a printed book that can be purchased at conferences and online via Amazon; (b) completing solicitations for presenting at Head Start national, regional, state, and organization conferences; (c) presenting the findings through training and seminars; and (d) seeking publication via professional newsletters and magazines with the Community Action Agency network, State Head Start Associations, and Regional Head Start Associations. This study will also be available through the ProQuest Central database. I will also seek to publish this study in an academic business journal and professional business publications. I will share a summary of the findings of this study with the participants.

Recommendations for Further Research

The fact that participants' perceptions about communication strategies are solely dependent upon their experiences within their organizational context was one of the primary limitations noted in this case study. To mitigate this limitation, further research

could expand the pool of participants to other geographical areas and increase the sample size. Four managers were selected to represent the sample and provide perspectives on the research question. Further research in other geographical areas would enhance the generalizability of the findings of this study. Generalizability adds validity to research findings, especially when the finding can be replicated through one of four types of replication, including exact, study-design, methodological, and theory-test (Urminsky & Dietvorst, 2024). If this exact study were conducted in a different geographical area and the findings were the same, this would add validity to the results of this case study. For this study, data were only collected from a Head Start program located in the Northern Region of the United States. I recommend that future studies focus on other target populations to gain a better understanding of these findings based on the Head Start industry's uniqueness. The entire industry may not be fully represented by the sample of participants in this study.

The data collection process was focused on mid-level managers or senior executives, and I would recommend a data collection process focused on exploring non-management employee experiences with the implementation of the communication strategies to increase profitability for further research. The concept of input from both the leaders and the employees would further explore the phenomenon by understanding the employee viewpoint. According to Allam et al. (2024), early employee involvement, an open and trusting organizational culture, and regular clear communication are critical to successfully implementing organizational change. I recommend further qualitative

research on the post-implementation of communication strategies. Such research could provide knowledge on the effectiveness of the implementation process.

Participants were encouraged during the semistructured interview process to be honest about their experiences to reduce the potential limitation that participants may only share what they thought I wanted to hear. Two research participants shared, during the interview process, a communication frustration related to navigating the implementation of strategies up the organizational hierarchy to senior management as having posed significant challenges. Participants shared recurring negative opinions related to senior management practices that created unnecessary delays, barriers, and problems with communication strategy execution. PAR-1 expressed the challenges as an opportunity in lessons in communication up the chain of command: “I learned that managing up had its own set of rules and rewards especially when trying to implement organization-wide strategies and you are not in the Chief Executive position.” Communication checks and balances included polite and respectful beg to differ, reminders of repercussions of decisions, and strong suggestions. Implementing these strategies provided opportunities to practice effective communication skills up the chain of command.

While PAR-3 expressed: “Although communication strategies have been very effective with mid-level managers, we have experienced significant failures with upper management communication due to the lack of consistent oversight, decision making, accountability, integrity, and inconsistency.” Mid-level managers showed that they were extremely competent in their program areas and took on an overwhelming amount of

work responsibility, which started to cause burnout due to the lack of support they needed from senior leadership. Both participants stressed the importance of buy-in from senior organizational leadership before implementing a new organization-wide communications strategy. Participant experiences call for a comprehensive review of the traditional hierarchical organization communication structure. Senior leadership could benefit from engaging in free and open communication with middle managers to take advantage of their operational knowledge and strategic insight. Future research is recommended regarding organizational factors influencing strategy implementation, including potential barriers and the contribution of senior leadership in the implementation process. Also, I recommend further research into successful communication strategies for communicating up the hierarchical chain of command to senior leadership.

Reflections

As a Director of Finance at a Head Start program, I had a personal interest in this research topic. The motivation for this study originated from work-related experiences involving communication silos between fiscal and program managers in Head Start programs. I recognized the challenges of effective management communication strategies that negatively impacted organizational profitability. In my experience, program managers in Head Start are subject matter experts in their content or service area. Few program managers obtained knowledge beyond their field of specialization, which sometimes prevented them from a holistic approach to serving the children, families, and community of their Head Start program. I observed the impactful power of collaboration when program managers came together to develop strategies for family and children's

success. I believed that if two diverse content areas could develop successful strategies for our external stakeholders, there had to be successful communication strategies to increase fiscal and program communications. I wanted to become a more effective leader and facilitate positive change at the organizations I consult with.

My personal interest created a heightened awareness of possible personal bias or preconceived ideas and values prior to conducting this research. To reduce potential personal bias, I made every effort to remain curious and intentionally focus on the views and perceptions of the participants during research exploration. I observed strict adherence to the interview protocol (see Appendix B) when I conducted the semistructured interviews to prevent inserting my personal feelings toward the topic of investigation. Using the interview protocol helped me to ensure that participants responded to each question and ensured consistency during the semistructured interview process. The interviews and subsequent analysis allowed me to gain a perspective on challenges and trends in the industry, while gaining knowledge of communication strategies implemented to mitigate siloes and increase profitability. In addition, to mitigate personal bias, I completed the member checking process during the data collection phase of the case study. The member checking process afforded participants an opportunity to validate my written interpretations of their responses by correcting, confirming, or providing additional information. My views and thinking regarding the research topic did not change as a result of completing the study. The research findings aligned with my professional experience.

Obtaining my doctoral degree is the pinnacle of my educational goals. As a professed life learner, I am always seeking opportunities for professional and personal development. When I started this journey, I had recently set up my own limited liability corporation (LLC) in preparation for my second career as a full-time adjunct professor and nonprofit fiscal consultant. Teaching and consulting work are my passions. The goal of earning this doctorate was to help me finalize my business plans and to ensure that I had the credentials necessary to effectively market myself and my new business and facilitate my transition to the educational arena. When I reflect on my journey, I am humbled, grateful, and blessed for the experience. I am appreciative for my remarkably, exceptionally supportive circle of family and friends who understood my pursuit and consistently encouraged and pushed me during the days of frustration and tiredness. I had a phenomenal committee who were unwavering in their commitment to my success, patient with my re-writes, diligently sharpened and fine-tuned my writing skills, challenged my thought processes, and provided me with feedback that was insightful, and thoughtful, which allowed me to stay true to my voice while driving me to excellence. I am proud of this milestone accomplishment. The journey was long, and each phase helped me to become proficient in my topic. I am excited to see what new endeavors lie ahead.

In conclusion, the DBA doctoral study process and experience were rigorous and challenged me to find my academic voice. Conducting the research study enhanced my knowledge base concerning research methods, designs, and analysis. I am grateful for the opportunities to develop skills in scholarly writing, citations, and interviewing

participants through a qualitative research lens and conceptual framework afforded during the doctoral case study process. Overall, the doctoral study process was rewarding and enlightened me in a number of positive ways that included (a) improved my communications and interpersonal skills, (b) broadened my capacity and knowledge for researching and solving business problems, (c) inspired me to impact positive organizational culture change and behaviors, and (d) enhanced my understanding of the leader's role to influence organizational change. Finally, the entire doctoral study process has been an impactful experience, and I look forward to motivating and empowering others through the knowledge and experiences I gained.

Conclusion

The study included an exploration of successful communication strategies to mitigate siloes and increase profitability. The organization that participated in this study achieved consistent and sustained profitability through the implementation of communication strategies to mitigate siloes between program and fiscal operations in their Head Start program. Five themes that emerged from the research included (a) leadership role, (b) organizational culture change, (c) meeting frequency and inclusive attendance, (d) access to data, and (e) training. The findings of this study aligned with existing literature regarding how strategies driven by the organization's leadership that implemented organizational culture changes through formalized communications channels significantly improved an organization's success rate by eliminating and mitigating communication silos.

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Appendix A: Interview Questions

Q1 – Describe the existing communications environment between program and financial operations at your organization used to increase profitability?

Q2 – What business strategies have you implemented to increase communications between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

Q3 – How did the program and fiscal staff respond to the implementation of these business strategies?

Q4 – How did your organization assess the effectiveness of the strategies for increasing communication between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

Q5 – Based upon your experiences, in what ways did this business strategy increase internal communications between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

Q6 – What business strategies did you find worked best for improving communications between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

Q7 – What lessons did you learn from implementing these business strategies?

Q8 – What, if anything, would you have done differently if given an opportunity to develop and implement these or another type of business strategy to increase communications to increase profitability?

Q9 – What additional information would you like to share about business strategies to increase communications between program and financial operations to increase profitability?

Appendix B: Interview Protocol

Researcher: Hi, my name is Maryom McCloud, I am a researcher in the Doctorate of Business Administration program at Walden University. How are you today? Thank you for agreeing to participate in this case study. May I begin the audio recording?

Participant: agrees with a verbal “yes.”

Researcher: Please state your name for the record.

Participant: states their name.

Researcher: This is a new study about communication strategies to mitigate functional silos in Head Start programs may help business leaders to increase communications between program and financial operations. For this study, you are invited to describe your experiences about communication strategies to mitigate functional siloes in Head Start programs. Here are a few things to note before we begin:

About this study:

- This interview should be no longer than 30-60 minutes.
- There will be only one interview session; however, the researcher may contact you to clarify and ensure the accuracy of recorded responses.
- The interview is being recorded via audio recording (no video recording)
- To protect your privacy, the published study will not share any names or details that identify you.
- You will be asked 9 research questions, please answer these questions to the best of your knowledge and experience.

Researcher: Are you ready to begin?

Participant: Yes

Researcher: ask each interview question. See Appendix A for the interview questions.

Researcher: This concludes the research interview. Thank you again for your participation. Do you have any questions for me or additional comments? If none, have a great day.